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Master's Thesis

Phytase-Active Bacteria for Plant-Based Food Fermentations

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Preface

This MSc thesis is the result of my time as a student at the University of Copenhagen, to whom I am deeply grateful for offering me the opportunity to undertake this project in close collaboration with the Section for Food Microbiology, Gut Health, and Fermentation. In this regard, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my principal supervisor, Lene Jespersen. Lene, since I first contacted you more than a year ago regarding the possibility of carrying out my MSc thesis under your supervision, you have demonstrated openness and confidence from the very beginning. Your expertise and experience within microbiology and food science have been invaluable throughout the preparation of this thesis. You have succeeded in creating the framework for a purposeful project that has been both challenging and highly educational.

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Finally, I would like to devote a few sentences to outlining the broader context of this MSc thesis. In addition to serving an educational purpose, the intention of this project has been to contribute to future scientific work being prepared by the section. For this reason, certain material marked “preparation only” has been included, indicating preparatory work intended for future use. Such content will be excluded from consideration in the results and discussion sections.

Enjoy your reading,
Kristoffer Krabbe

Abstract

The present study investigated the phytic acid-hydrolysing capabilities of food-grade bacterial strains belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus*, and *Lactiplantibacillus* with the aim of improving the nutritional bioavailability of plant-based proteinaceous foods. Through *in silico* analyses, phytase-encoding genes were identified across all three genera, including the first reported detection of a protein tyrosine phosphatase-like phytase gene (*phyLp*) in *Lactiplantibacillus*. Although strains of *Limosilactobacillus* did not exhibit detectable phytase activity under the applied conditions, selected strains of *Bacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* demonstrated phytase-producing capabilities during initial screening procedures. In particular, *B. subtilis* Natto and PRO55 emerged as the most effective candidates and were subsequently evaluated in a faba bean medium fermentation model. Fermentation with these strains resulted in a significant reduction in phytic acid levels relative to negative controls. Collectively, these findings supports that bacterial fermentation constitutes a promising approach for improving the nutritional quality of plant-based proteinaceous foods. However, the study also underscores the considerable strain-specific variability associated with phytic acid degradation. Future research should therefore focus on elucidating regulatory mechanisms and investigating synergistic co-culture strategies to further optimise fermentation-mediated phytic acid reduction procedures.

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1 Introduction

Global demand for dietary protein is increasing rapidly as a result of population growth and rising incomes (Clinthorne et al., 2026). However, conventional animal-based protein production is associated with significant constraints related to sustainability, resource consumption, and greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, the transition toward more sustainable food systems requires the development of alternative protein sources. Nevertheless, the nutritional bioavailability of plant-based foods is often reduced by the presence of antinutritional factors (Y. Kumar et al., 2022). Antinutrients are plant metabolites that function primarily as defensive compounds against herbivores and other biotic stressors. When consumed by humans in sufficiently high quantities, these compounds may exert adverse effects, including nutrient absorption inhibition (Das et al., 2022). Phytic acid (PA), a major antinutrient, is accumulated in high concentrations in legumes, where it diminishes the bioavailability of minerals and proteins (Rickard & Thompson, 1997).

Fermentation is a widely employed technique in food processing and has shown to effectively reduce PA levels in legumes (Adebiyi et al., 2019). During fermentation, the degradation of PA is attributed to the activity of phytate-degrading enzymes produced endogenously by the fermenting microorganisms (Gupta et al., 2015). In the present study, fermentation was investigated as a strategy for reducing PA content in plant-based fermentations through the evaluation of the PA-hydrolysing capabilities of food-grade bacteria belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus*, and *Lactiplantibacillus*.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Phytic Acid

2.1.1 Phytic Acid Structure and Sources

Myo-inositol-1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakisphosphate (InsP_6), or PA, is the most abundant derivative of the numerous phosphorylated *myo*-inositol compounds. PA is characterised by containing the cyclic alcohol, *myo*-inositol, as the carbon backbone to which phosphate groups are attached via phosphomonoester bonds (Raboy, 2003) (Figure 1). Molar weight of PA is $660.04 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and its molecular formula is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{24}\text{P}_6$. In PA, the phosphates at position C1, C3, C4, C5 and C6 are equatorially attached, whereas the phosphate at position C2 is axially attached (Johnson & Tate, 1969). The attached phosphate groups gives PA its unique characteristics, as these provides 12 ionizable protons responsible for its strong chelating properties. Due to this, PA shows great affinity towards polyvalent cations in the following decreasing order of stability: $\text{Cu}^{+2} > \text{Zn}^{+2} > \text{Ni}^{+2} > \text{Co}^{+2} > \text{Mn}^{+2} > \text{Fe}^{+2} > \text{Ca}^{+2}$ (Graf & Eaton, 1990). When such chelation occurs, water-insoluble salts, called phytates, are produced.

Table 1: Phytic acid content of cereals, pseudocereals and legumes.

Product	Item	Phytic acid (%) (w w⁻¹)	Reference
Cereals	Barley	0.56	(Lehrfeld, 1994)
	Brown rice	0.99	(Ravindran et al., 1994)
	Maize	1.15	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Oat	0.79–1.01	(Lolas et al., 1976)
	Polished rice	0.60	(Ravindran et al., 1994)
	Rye	0.57	(Lehrfeld, 1994)
	Sorghum	1.08	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Triticale	1.29	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Wheat	0.39–1.35	(Frossard et al., 2000)
Pseudocereals	Amaranth	1.39	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Buckwheat	1.42	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Quinoa	0.97	(Egli et al., 2002)
Legumes	Blackeyed bean	0.86	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Chickpeas	0.75–0.96	(Chitra et al., 1995; Duhan et al., 1989)
	Cowpeas	0.66	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Dwarf bean	1.13	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Faba bean	0.80–1.37	(Zehring et al., 2022)
	Great Northern bean	1.12	(Lehrfeld, 1994)
	Lentil	0.71	(Ravindran et al., 1994)
	Lima bean	0.84	(Lehrfeld, 1994)
	Lucerne	1.36	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Lupin	0.67	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Mungbean	0.83	(Egli et al., 2002)
	Navy bean	0.75–1.58	(Lolas & Markakis, 1975)
	Pea	0.72–1.23	(Hanakahi & West, 2002)
	Peanut	1.86–2.31	(Lazarte et al., 2015)
Pinto bean	0.61–0.64	(Lolas & Markakis, 1975)	
Soy	1.01–1.47	(Lolas et al., 1976)	
White bean	1.08	(Egli et al., 2002)	

PA is ubiquitous in eukaryotic organisms, but is most often present in cereals, legumes, nuts, oilseeds, tubers, pollen and spores (Sasakawa et al., 1995). In legumes and cereals, PA comprise 1% to 5% (w w⁻¹, dry weight basis), where it functions as the primary reserve of phosphorous, accounting for 50-85% of the total phosphorus level (Ravindran et al., 1994; Thavarajah et al., 2010). An overview of PA content of common cereals and legumes is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Structure of myo-inositol-1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakisphosphate: phytic acid.

Apart from serving as phosphorous reserve, PA has shown to serve in a number of other functionalities. PA, and its more highly phosphorylated pyrophosphate-containing derivatives, are additionally involved as a secondary messenger in signal transduction and regulation (Safrany et al., 1999), RNA export, DNA repair and recombination (Hanakahi & West, 2002; Luo et al., 2002; York et al., 1999), in endocytosis and vesicular trafficking (Saiardi et al., 2002), and as an anti-oxidative agent (Graf & Eaton, 1990).

2.1.2 Phytic Acid Biosynthesis in Plants

The PA content is highest in growing seeds compared to tissues such as leaves and stems, and accumulation can typically be detected during the seed maturation period (Rasmussen et al., 2010; H. Sharma et al., 2023). In a study by Raboy and Dickinson (1987) investigating the rate of synthesis and accumulation of PA in soybean, it was reported that each soybean seed accumulated 18.7 mg day⁻¹. After its synthesis, PA is stored in globoids (crystalline inclusions) within the cell's protein bodies (Iwai et al., 2012). The synthesis of cytosolic PA can be carried out following one of two distinct pathways: 1) lipid-independent synthesis or 2) lipid-dependent synthesis. In seeds of cereals and legumes, the lipid-independent pathway is predominant (Rasmussen et al., 2010).

In the lipid-independent synthesis of PA (Figure 2), the initial step is the conversion of glucose 6-phosphate into *myo*-inositol-3-phosphate (Ins3P), catalysed by the *myo*-inositol-3-phosphate synthase (MIPS). This reaction remains the only known *de novo*

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the lipid-independent synthesis of phytic acid in plants. Adapted from Rasmussen et al. (2010). Abbreviations: *myo*-inositol-3-phosphate synthase (MIPS); inositol tris/tetrakisphosphate kinase (ITPK); inositol pentakisphosphate 2-kinase (IPK1).

pathway for synthesising the inositol ring in plants (Loewus & Murthy, 2000), and it has been reported that the genes encoding MIPS are highly expressed in developing seeds in both rice and soy bean (Chappell et al., 2006; Suzuki et al., 2007). After the formation of *Ins3P*, a consecutive and stepwise phosphorylation occurs of the remaining carbons, with C2 being phosphorylated last as the only axially attached phosphate. In this process, *Ins3P* is converted into *myo*-inositol-1,3,4,5,6-5-phosphate [*Ins(1,3,4,5,6)P₅*] by the enzyme inositol tris/tetrakisphosphate kinase (ITPK). In the study by Suzuki et al. (2007), the ITPK encoding genes was suggested to possess multi-kinase activity, ultimately resulting in multiple intermediate pathways for yielding *Ins(1,3,4,5,6)P₅* from *Ins3P*. Once the equatorially positioned phosphates are attached to the inositol ring, the final phosphate is attached at position C2 in a reaction carried out by the enzyme inositol pentakisphosphate 2-kinase (IPK1), ultimately yielding PA (*InsP₆*).

Several biotic and abiotic factors are suggested to influence the PA synthesis in grains and seeds, including geographical location, climate and environmental variations, irrigation conditions, soil type and structure, as well as genotypic variations to the plant varieties (Loewus, 2001). In a study by Thavarajah et al. (2010), the effects of temperature on PA content in 11 lentil genotypes was investigated, and a significant increase in

PA synthesis during seed maturation was reported at higher temperatures. Germination time has additionally been suggested to impact the PA content, to which Khattak et al. (2007) reported a significant decrease in PA content in chickpeas after 48 hours of germination. Furthermore, differences in hormonal concentrations during seed maturation has been suggested to regulate the synthesis of PA in plants. In relation to this, Matsuno and Fujimura (2014) investigated the effect of abscisic acid on PA synthesis and reported a regulatory effect, with increasing concentrations of abscisic acid upregulating the production of PA.

2.1.3 Health Effects of Phytic Acid

It is generally accepted that PA demonstrates both antinutritional and beneficial effects to human health, and while some studies emphasises the important benefits of PA in human nutrition, PA has still been characterised as an anti-nutrient (Feizollahi et al., 2021; J. R. Zhou & Erdman Jr., 1995). As any review on PA would be incomplete without considering both paradigms, the following section will review both the antinutritional and beneficial effects of PA.

Anti-Oxidative Effects of Phytic Acid Oxidation is in many cases considered a destructive process in food, as oxidation reactions can lead to flavour changes, discoloration, nutritional losses and microbiological spoilage (V. Kumar et al., 2010). In food, especially unsaturated fatty acids and iron are susceptible to oxidation in the presence of oxygen. These oxidation reactions can be limited by the presence of an antioxidant, to which the strong chelating properties of PA makes it a natural antioxidant (Graf & Eaton, 1990). The ability of PA to chelate iron to form a catalytically inactive compound is considered a crucial mechanism in the inhibition of iron-driven hydroxyl radical ($-OH\cdot$) formation (Graf et al., 1984). This will ultimately suppress the oxidative stress and potentially inhibit oxidation reactions, such as lipid peroxidation, important in food. In the study by (Graf et al., 1984), the antioxidative properties of 22 iron chelators were investigated from which PA was concluded to be the most effective and nontoxic anti-oxidant.

The ability of PA to chelate iron also enables it to reduce the production of warmed-over flavour (WOF). WOFs are formed during cooking of animal proteins, as myoglobin releases substantial amounts of free iron which then, by complexing with phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), catalyses the rapid autooxidation of its unsaturated fatty acyl moieties (Graf & Panter, 1991). In this case, PA can inhibit the formation of WOFs by either replacing the iron from PE or by chelating iron to form the catalytically inactive compounds (V. Kumar et al., 2010).

Anti-Carcinogenic Effects of Phytic Acid Apart from its role as a natural anti-oxidant due to its strong chelating properties, PA have also been suggested to serve as

a broad-spectrum anti-carcinogenic agent (Vucenik & Shamsuddin, 2003). Studies have reported inhibited growth of human colon cancer cells (Sakamoto et al., 1993) and human leukemic hematopoietic cells (Deliliers et al., 2002) when exposed to PA. Furthermore, PA has also shown to reduce the proliferation of cervical cancer cells (Ferry et al., 2002), prostate cancer cells (R. P. Singh et al., 2003) and breast cancer cells (Shamsuddin et al., 1996). In relation to this, it was concluded by Vucenik and Shamsuddin (2003) that the anti-carcinogenic effect of PA is much dependent on time and dose, and that several mechanisms of actions are present.

As for the proposed mechanism of action, PA is considered to possess natural killer activity towards tumour cells (Baten et al., 1989), stimulate gene expression for greater cell differentiation (Saied & Shamsuddin, 1998), as well as induce alteration in signal transduction relevant for cancer prevention (Dong et al., 1999). Additionally, the role of PA as an antioxidative agent is considered significant in inhibiting the formation of cancer cells through the suppression of oxidative stress within cells (Graf & Eaton, 1990).

2.1.4 Phytic Acid as an Antinutrient

At physiological pH, the phosphate groups of PA are negatively charged, enabling it to bind positively charged molecules such as minerals and proteins. In such cases, the physiochemical properties of the produced complexes alter from that of the original state, which can ultimately result in reduced nutritional bioavailability (Rickard & Thompson, 1997). On the basis of these characteristics, PA is classified as an antinutritional factor when present in food matrices. PA and its interactions is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Possible interactions of phytic acid with A) minerals, B) positively charged proteins, and C) negatively charged proteins. Adapted from Wang and Guo (2021).

Phytic Acid : Mineral Interaction PA in human nutrition is considered to reduce mineral uptake, to which especially divalent ions such as zinc, iron, calcium, magnesium, and copper are of concern (Konietzny & Greiner, 2003). When PA is present in the diet, it can chelate mineral ions to form PA–mineral complexes that are insoluble at physiological pH values and, consequently, are not bioavailable for intestinal absorption. As neither the gastrointestinal tract itself nor its inherent microbiota possesses the ability to produce PA-degrading enzymes (Iqbal et al., 1994), humans has as no effective mechanism to counteract the reduced bioavailability. Regarding the impact of PA on nutritional quality, a study demonstrated that the presence of 2, 25, and 250 mg in a wheat roll reduced zinc absorption in humans by 18%, 64%, and 82%, respectively (Coulibaly et al., 2011).

Among the previously mentioned minerals, Zn^{2+} deficiency arising from complex formation with PA is regarded as the most critical concern for human health (Lopez et al., 2002). For individuals consuming exclusively plant-based diets, PA plays a significant role in regulating Zn^{2+} homeostasis due to its suppressive effect on zinc absorption; consequently, reduced zinc uptake may contribute to conditions such as dwarfism and hypogonadism (Oberleas, 1983). In addition, PA has been shown to reduce the absorption of non-haem iron and Ca^{2+} in humans, although its effect on Ca^{2+} absorption appears to be less pronounced than its suppressive effects on Zn^{2+} and $Fe^{2+/3+}$ absorption (Brune et al., 1992; Lopez et al., 2002).

The stability and solubility of PA-mineral complexes are influenced by several factors, including the type of mineral, pH level, the PA:mineral molar ratio, and the presence of other compounds (Oberleas, 1983). The complexes formed when PA binds to minerals are soluble at acidic conditions, and insoluble at physiological pH (Dendougui & Schwedt, 2004). Among the PA–mineral complexes of interest, PA– Ca^{2+} , PA– Zn^{2+} , and PA– Cu^{2+} complexes are insoluble at pH values above 4–5, whereas precipitation of PA– Mg^{2+} complexes occurs at pH values exceeding 7 (Brown et al., 1961; Nolan et al., 1987). Conversely, PA– Fe^{2+} is not easily precipitated, and PA– Fe^{3+} precipitation begins below pH 4 with increasing solubility above (Nissar et al., 2017). Furthermore, PA-mineral complexes can interact with other dietary minerals in an indirect manner; i.e. when PA binds a mineral, complexation with additional minerals can subsequently occur (Nissar et al., 2017). For instance, PA– Ca^{2+} complex exhibits greater affinity towards Zn^{2+} , ultimately reducing the bioavailability of both minerals (V. Kumar et al., 2010; Nissar et al., 2017).

Phytic Acid : Protein Interaction The charge of proteins is dependent on pH. At conditions where pH is below their isoelectric point, proteins are positively charged which enables them to form complexes with PA due to electrostatic charges (Cheryan, 1980). When this occurs, insoluble complexes are formed that are only dissolvable below pH 3.5 (Nissar et al., 2017). Complexation between PA and proteins are known to occur at both acidic and alkaline conditions (Cheryan, 1980). When pH is above the isoelectric point of

the protein, both PA and the protein is negatively charged. However, complexation can still occur in the presence of a multivalent cation, in which a soluble protein-cation-PA complex is formed (Nissar et al., 2017). The formation of PA-protein or PA-cation-protein complexes can ultimately result in reduced protein digestibility, as proteolytic enzymes are prevented from exerting activity. In relation to this, *in vitro* studies have shown that proteins bound by PA are less prone to digestion by proteolytic enzymes such as pepsin, trypsin and chymotrypsin (Deshpande & Damodaran, 1989; M. Singh & Krikorian, 1982). Furthermore, Ding et al. (2024) reported lower *in vitro* digestibility of soy protein isolates at increasing PA concentrations.

2.1.5 Effects of Processing on Phytic Acid Content

Several food-processing techniques, including soaking, germination, cooking, and fermentation, can promote the hydrolysis of PA. The enhanced degradation of PA during these processes is often attributed to increased activity of endogenous PA-hydrolysing enzymes, phytases, derived from plants and microorganisms (V. Kumar et al., 2010).

Soaking In the processing of cereals and legumes, soaking is often used as a pretreatment in various production schemes. PA is soluble in water, and its reduction in food during soaking can be attributed to two distinct mechanisms: 1) the activity of plant-endogenous phytases, and 2) the leaching of PA into the soaking medium (Coulibaly et al., 2011). Due to changed physiochemical properties of PA-mineral and -protein complexes, leaching will be influenced by the nature of PA, as well as the pH of the soaking medium (Albarracín et al., 2013; Mahgoub & Elhag, 1998). In relation to the activity of endogenous phytases, soaking temperature has been reported to be of significant importance, with higher activity observed at temperatures closer to the enzymatic optimum (Carlson & Poulsen, 2003).

Germination Germination is a method of sprouting seeds like grains and legumes to improve their nutritional profile, digestibility, and functional properties. Germination is the process by which uptake of water by the inactive dry seed is initiated, and development of embryonic axis is the result (Rifna et al., 2019). Therefore, the initial step in germination is a soaking process where the moisture content is elevated to favourable conditions for metabolic/enzymatic activity (Coulibaly et al., 2011). During germination, hydrolysis of PA is dependent on the activity of plant-endogenous phytases, and the activity of these has been reported highest after 4 days of germination (Greiner et al., 2000). Furthermore, the composition of the germination medium has been reported to influence the hydrolysis of PA. In this context, Sattar et al. (1990) observed greater PA hydrolysis during germination in distilled water compared with tap water, which was attributed to the presence of cations in tap water capable of forming PA–mineral complexes.

Fermentation Fermentation is an extensively used method for processing of many different foods. In this context, fermentation is aimed at providing desirable biochemical changes to the food, triggered by microorganisms and their endogenous enzymes (Coulibaly et al., 2011). In relation to PA, it is namely the microorganism’s native phytases that are considered responsible for the reduction of PA during fermentation of foods, and factors such as the initial concentration of PA, fermentation conditions, and the strains used can affect the degree of PA hydrolysis (Bilgiçli & İbanoğlu, 2007; Feizollahi et al., 2021). Owing to its large molecular structure and negative charge, PA cannot readily diffuse across bacterial cell membranes. Consequently, phytases synthesised by bacteria must be secreted extracellularly in order to catalyse the hydrolysis of PA.

Whether being alkaline or acidic, favourable conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis of PA, such as optimum pH, can be provided by fermentation (Gupta et al., 2015). In a study by Adebisi et al. (2019) assessing nutritional qualities of dawadawa (an African fermented condiment made from legumes), a significant reduction of PA (18.1%) was observed, with its reduction being attributed to the enzymatic activity of the indigenous fermenting microorganisms. Dawadawa is produced mainly through alkaline fermentation, with *Bacillus* spp. being the predominant fermenting microorganisms (Antai & Ibrahim, 1986). With respect to acidic fermentations, El Hag et al. (2002) reported a significant reduction of PA (59.7%) during fermentation of pearl millet dough, with mixed cultures of yeast and lactobacilli considered the predominant fermenting microorganisms.

2.1.6 Methodologies for Determining Phytic Acid Content

Determination of PA in biological samples has historically posed significant analytical challenges due to its strong metal-binding properties, structural similarity to other inositol phosphates, and the complexity of biological matrices. Over time, methodologies have evolved from classical precipitation-based techniques to more advanced chromatographic approaches. A comprehensive review of analytical methodologies for the determination of PA has been provided by Marolt and Kolar (2020), and the subsequent sections are largely based on, and adapted from, their work.

Classic Analytical Methods Early analytical methods were primarily based on precipitation reactions involving multivalent metal ions. The method introduced by Heubner and Stadler (1919) relied on extraction of PA from biological samples with hydrochloric acid, followed by titration with ferric chloride in the presence of ammonium thiocyanate. In this assay, PA forms an insoluble complex with Fe^{3+} , and the titration endpoint is indicated by the appearance of red-coloured iron(III) thiocyanate complex.

Further refinements, such as those introduced by McCance and Widdowson (1935), incorporated multiple processing steps including acid extraction, neutralisation, precipitation with ferric ions, and subsequent separation of the precipitate. The PA-bound

iron was then converted to iron hydroxide under alkaline conditions, releasing phytates into solution. This was followed by hydrolysis using Kjeldahl digestion (Padmanabhan & Sundaram, 1955) and colorimetric determination of orthophosphate (P_i) via the molybdenum blue reaction (Briggs, 1922). Although these methods facilitated quantification of phytic phosphorus in food matrices, they were highly labour-intensive, time-consuming, and subject to substantial analytical constraints. (Marolt & Kolar, 2020)

The primary limitations of precipitation-based techniques stem from three key factors. First, the stoichiometry of the PA-iron complex is not fixed and varies depending on pH, ionic strength, and the presence of competing multivalent cations such as Ca^{2+} (Thompson & Erdman Jr., 1982). This variability compromises the reproducibility and accuracy of quantification. Second, these methods lack selectivity, as other phosphorylated compounds, including lower inositol phosphates (Ins P_1 through Ins P_5) and inorganic phosphates, can also form insoluble complexes with Fe^{3+} , leading to overestimation of PA content. Third, relatively large sample quantities are required to achieve measurable titration endpoints, limiting applicability in studies with scarce or valuable biological materials. Consequently, results generated using these classical methodologies should be interpreted with caution, particularly when applied to complex food matrices that are rich in mineral ions and phytate degradation products. (Marolt & Kolar, 2020)

Liquid Chromatography Separation Methods The introduction of liquid chromatography techniques marked a significant advancement in PA analysis. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) enabled direct separation and quantification of inositol phosphates, improving both specificity and analytical resolution. Early applications employed reversed-phase columns coupled with refractive index detection for the analysis of PA in food samples (Camire & Clydesdale, 1982; Graf & Dintzis, 1982; Knuckles et al., 1982; Tangendjaja et al., 1980). However, these initial methods suffered from poor separation efficiency, as PA often co-eluted with the solvent. (Marolt & Kolar, 2020)

To address these limitations, the addition of ion-pairing reagents to the mobile phase enhanced retention and separation of highly polar inositol phosphates on reversed-phase columns (Foda, 1995). Optimization of pH conditions further enabled the resolution of multiple inositol phosphate species, including Ins P_3 through Ins P_6 . These improvements allowed for more accurate profiling of PA and its partially dephosphorylated derivatives in complex biological samples. Additional methodological developments incorporated sample purification steps to improve analytical selectivity. For example, strong anion-exchange chromatography was used prior to HPLC analysis to remove lower inositol phosphates (Ins P_1 and Ins P_2), thereby facilitating the quantification of higher phosphorylated species in food matrices such as legumes (Burbano et al., 1995). Such approaches significantly enhanced the reliability of quantification in nutritionally relevant samples. (Marolt & Kolar, 2020)

In summary, the analytical determination of PA has progressed from non-specific, labour-intensive precipitation assays to more advanced chromatographic techniques offering improved selectivity and resolution. While classical methods laid the foundation for early investigations, their inherent limitations necessitated the adoption of modern separation-based approaches. HPLC, particularly when combined with ion-pairing strategies and appropriate sample preparation, has emerged as a robust tool for the analysis of PA and related inositol phosphates in biological matrices.

2.2 Microbial Phosphate Starvation Strategies

Phosphorus is a vital cellular element, ranking fifth in abundance, and play key roles in genetic inheritance, energy metabolism, membrane structure, and intracellular signalling. In bacteria, it is primarily acquired as P_i . However, P_i is often scarce in natural environments, prompting bacteria and other organisms to evolve adaptive mechanisms to efficiently acquire and conserve this essential nutrient. (Santos-Beneit, 2015)

2.2.1 The Bacterial Pho Regulon

The phosphate (Pho) regulon constitutes a global regulatory network that controls P_i acquisition and homeostasis in bacteria. It was first characterised in *Escherichia coli* (Wanner & Chang, 1987) and has subsequently been identified across a wide range of bacterial species. This regulon typically induces the expression of genes encoding extracellular enzymes, such as phytases, which facilitate the release of P_i from organic substrates. Regulation of the Pho regulon is mediated by a two-component signal transduction system comprising an inner-membrane histidine kinase sensor and a cytoplasmic response regulator (Figure 4). While the functional architecture of this system is conserved, its nomenclature varies among species, including PhoR–PhoB in *Escherichia coli* (Tomassen et al., 1982), PhoR–PhoP in *Bacillus subtilis* (Hulett et al., 1994), PnpR–PnpS in *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Novak et al., 1999), and PhoR–PhoS in *Corynebacterium glutamicum* (Kočan et al., 2006).

Under conditions of P_i limitation, the sensor kinase undergoes autophosphorylation and subsequently transfers the phosphate group to a conserved aspartate residue in the response regulator. Upon activation, the phosphorylated regulator binds to specific DNA sequences to either induce or repress gene expression. These regulatory elements, termed PHO boxes, were first identified in *E. coli* and originally defined as 18-nucleotide motifs composed of two 7-nucleotide direct repeats separated by four variable bases (Makino et al., 1988). However, the consensus sequence of PHO-boxes varies among species, reflecting differences in regulator:DNA interactions (Blanco et al., 2002).

Notably, several experimentally validated PHO boxes have been identified in genes that do not exhibit clear P_i -dependent regulation, whereas some well-established mem-

Figure 4: Bacterial Pho-regulon two-component regulatory system. The system is comprised of an inner-membrane histidine kinase sensor protein (PhoR) and a cytoplasmic transcriptional response regulator (PhoP).

bers of the Pho regulon lack recognisable conserved PHO box motifs (Allenby et al., 2012; Martín et al., 2012). These observations indicate that additional sequence features, together with the participation of auxiliary regulatory proteins or small-molecule ligands, likely contribute to the complexity of Pho regulon regulation. Depletion of P_i in the environment is a key trigger for activation of the Pho regulon in bacteria, unlike in other organisms such as *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, where intracellular P_i levels appear to govern this response (Auesukaree et al., 2004). Despite these findings, the molecular mechanisms underlying phosphate sensing and signal transduction to the response regulator remain incompletely resolved and are likely to differ among organisms.

2.2.2 Microbial Phytases

Phytases (*myo*-inositol 1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakisphosphate phosphohydrolase) are enzymes that sequentially cleaves groups of P_i from the *myo*-inositol backbone of PA, thereby serving a crucial role in the natural phosphorous cycle. Several classes of phytases have evolved in both bacteria and eukaryotes, of which three mechanistically distinct groups are considered relevant in the context of fermented foods: histidine acid phytases, β -propeller phytases, and protein tyrosine phosphatase-like phytases. The characterisation of these classes is based on differences in optimal pH or their unique catalytic mechanism. (Scott et al., 2024)

Histidine Acid Phytases The most well studied class of phytases, namely the histidine acid phytases (HAPhy), belongs to the histidine acid phosphatase superfamily, of which origin is primarily fungal. HAPHys are categorised into two groups: 1) histidine acid phosphatases with phytase activity (HP2Ps), and 2) multiple inositol polyphosphate phosphatases (MINPPs) (Acquistapace et al., 2020). HAPHys are merely capable of hydrolysing equatorially attached phosphate groups (yielding *myo*-inositol 2-monophosphate) and shows reduced affinity towards lower *myo*-inositol phosphates (Konietzny & Greiner, 2002; Wyss et al., 1999). HAPhy is considered the class of phytases with highest specific activity, ranging from 50 to >3000 U mg⁻¹ under optimal conditions (pH optimum: 5.0–5.5; temperature optimum: 55–58 °C) (Greiner & Konietzny, 2006).

There are two main structural domains of HAPHys, α/β and α , from which the positively charged active site/substrate binding pocket is located between the two (Figure 5) (Wyss et al., 1999). Since the active site is positively charged, a HAPhy is dependent on its substrate being negatively charged, as is the case with phosphate groups of PA. Through chelation with PA, cations are capable of disrupting the activity of HAPHys, as this reduces the electrostatic interactions between PA and the active site. Across enzymes from the histidine acid phosphatase superfamily, the α/β -domain is structurally conserved, whereas the α -domain is more variable. In recent evolution studies, it has become evident that the α domain structure and sequence characteristics are key determinants in HAPhy substrate specificity (Acquistapace et al., 2022; Herrmann et al., 2022; Rix et al., 2022). In a protein comparison by Scott et al. (2024), which grouped phytases according to structural similarities, it was reported that HAPHys were clustered primarily based on variation in the α -domain.

Figure 5: Active site and reaction mechanism of a histidine acid phytase from *Aspergillus niger*. Adapted from Scott et al. (2024).

In all HAPHys, the conserved motif RHGxRxP is present in the active site, and the distinction between the two groups of HAPHys lies in the catalytic domains which contains

the motifs HD and HAE for HP2Ps and MINPPs, respectively (Acquistapace et al., 2020). In both cases, it is the positively charged histidine residue in the substrate binding pocket that catalyses the nucleophile substitution of a negatively charged phosphate group of PA (Kostrewa et al., 1997). In this reaction, an aspartic acid residue in the active site functions as electron donor when the phosphomonoester bond is broken, and the previously attached phosphate is subsequently replaced with an alcohol group. The active site is regenerated as the now negatively charged aspartic acid residue reacts with water, ultimately releasing P_i . (Scott et al., 2024)

β -Propeller Phytases β -propeller phytases (BPPHy) are characterised by containing the archetypical β -propeller fold consisting of six β -sheets arranged in a ring (Figure 6). In contrast to HAPhys, BPPHy has a more basic pH optimum (pH 6.5–7.5), which is why they are typically referred to as alkaline phytases (Greiner & Konietzny, 2006). The active site of BPPHy is located in the conserved N-terminal β -propeller region, and contains the conserved motifs DAADDPAIW and NNVD which functions in the binding of Ca^{2+} (Shin et al., 2001). Once two Ca^{2+} are bound in the active site, a phosphate group of PA can be bound, and with a proton donated from either water or a basic amino acid, such as arginine or lysine, the phosphomonoester bond is broken (Scott et al., 2024; Shin et al., 2001).

Figure 6: Active site and reaction mechanism of a β -propeller phytase from *Bacillus subtilis*. Adapted from Scott et al. (2024).

In carrying out the hydrolysis of phosphate groups from PA, the active site of BPPHy recognises two adjacent phosphates and cleaves just one (Shin et al., 2001). As a result of this, BPPHy prefers the hydrolysis of every second phosphate group of PA eventually yielding either $Ins(1,3,5)P_3$ or $Ins(2,4,6)P_3$. Due to its unique structural features, BPPHy exhibits strong specificity for PA and generally displays higher activity toward $PA-Ca^{2+}$ complexes compared with HAPhys (Scott et al., 2024; Shin et al., 2001).

Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase-Like Phytases Protein tyrosine phosphatase-like phytases (PTPhy) were first identified among anaerobic bacterial species from the gut microbiota of ruminants, and are also known as cysteine phytases due to the identity of the catalytic residue (Yanke et al., 1998). PTPhys features a partial β -barrel domain along with a protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP) core domain made up of parallel β -sheets and several α -helices (Figure 7) (Puhl et al., 2007). Its active site resides within the PTP domain and includes the characteristic HCxxGxxRT motif. Optimal conditions for PTPhy includes pH 4.0–4.5, at which the specific activity ranges from 4 to >600 U mg^{-1} (Castillo Villamizar et al., 2019; Scott et al., 2024).

Figure 7: Active site and reaction mechanism of a protein tyrosine phosphatase-like phytase from *Selenomonas ruminantium*. Adapted from Scott et al. (2024).

The active site of PTPhys contains a positively charged arginine residue, responsible for binding the negatively charged phosphate group of PA. When such binding occurs, the thiolate anion of the catalytic cysteine residue reacts with the phosphate group to create a phosphocysteine intermediate (Chu et al., 2004). A proton is then donated from an aspartic acid residue in the active site, ultimately hydrolysing the phosphomonoester bond. The active site is regenerated when the aspartic acid residue takes a proton from a water molecule, which subsequently reacts with the phosphocysteine intermediate to release P_i (Chu et al., 2004). However, irreversible inactivation of the enzyme can occur as a result of oxidation of the thiolate anion in the active site (Gruninger et al., 2008).

Conformational differences of several loops within the PTP domain of PTPhys are known to impact the substrate specificity (Bruder et al., 2017). Even though these loops are not located within the active site, short loops in the PTP domain will alter the protein structure and create a more open binding pocket, allowing for several $\text{Ins}P_4$ compounds being produced from the hydrolysis of $\text{Ins}P_5$. In contrast, long loops in the PTP domain can cause conformational changes that inhibits the formation of certain $\text{Ins}P_4$ species (Bruder et al., 2017; Scott et al., 2024).

2.3 *Bacillus* in Fermented Foods

In the context of food fermentations, many products rely on yeast and/or lactic acid bacteria (LAB) as the major fermenting microbes, while the role of *Bacillus* in shaping food quality represents an emerging and comparatively underexplored area of research (Z. Li et al., 2023). Alkaline food fermentations using legumes as substrate are where *Bacillus* spp. frequently occur (Parkouda et al., 2009), and the consumption of such is of great importance in many East and South Asian countries (Liu et al., 2022). Within the *Bacillaceae* family, the gram-positive, rod-shaped, spore-forming *Bacillus* is one of the most ancient and diverse genera. Among the species within the *Bacillus* genera, the Food and Drug Administration has classified *B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. atrophaeus*, *B. clausii*, *B. coagulans*, *B. licheniformis*, and *B. subtilis* as “Generally Recognised as Safe” (GRAS) (Raman et al., 2025; Sewalt et al., 2016).

Of fermented legumes, the *B. subtilis* species is extensively used in producing the fermented condiments cheonggukjang and natto of Southeast Asian origin, as well as in West African fermented products such as gari and dawadawa (Raman et al., 2025). The role of *Bacillus* spp. in such fermented products include the production of extracellular enzymes such as amylases and proteases, among others. Additionally, *B. subtilis* is known for being effective producers of phytases, to which Phengnuam and Suntornsuk (2013) reported a 42% reduction of PA when fermenting the seeds of *Jatropha curcas* with *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*, thus highlighting the potential of alkaline *Bacillus*-mediated fermentations to effectively degrade PA.

2.3.1 *myo*-Inositol Metabolism in *Bacillus*

The compound *myo*-inositol is abundant in various environments, and several microorganisms including *B. subtilis* can grow on *myo*-inositol as sole carbon source (Yoshida et al., 1997). General for bacteria, *myo*-inositol catabolism is mediated by enzymes encoded by the *iol* operon. The composition of this operon varies among organisms, and the associated metabolic pathways are not yet fully elucidated across all bacterial genera. In *B. subtilis*, the *iolABCDEFGHIJ* operon is responsible for the catabolism of *myo*-Inositol, and the two genes *iolT* and *iolF* are responsible for transporting *myo*-inositol across the cell-membrane (Yoshida et al., 2002, 2008). Once *myo*-inositol has entered the cell, IolG is the enzyme responsible for the initial dehydrogenation of *myo*-inositol into 2-keto-*myo*-inositol (2KMI), utilising NAD⁺ in the process (Yasutaro et al., 1991). A dehydration step follows as 2KMI is converted to 3D-(3,5/4)-trihydroxycyclohexane-1,2-dione (THcHDO) by IolE (Yoshida et al., 2004). Subsequently, a hydrolysis of THcHDO catalysed by IolD yields 5-deoxy-d-glucuronic acid (5DG), which then undergoes isomerisation by IolB to produce 2-deoxy-5-keto-d-gluconic acid (DKG) (Yoshida et al., 2008). DKG is then phosphorylated by the kinase IolC to yield 2-deoxy-5-keto-d-gluconic acid 6-phosphate

Figure 8: *myo*-inositol catabolic pathways in *Bacillus subtilis* including functions of *iol* genes. Abbreviations for metabolic intermediates: 2-keto-*myo*-inositol (2KMI); 3D-(3,5/4)-trihydroxycyclohexane-1,2-dione (THcHDO); 5-deoxy-d-glucuronic acid (5DG); 2-deoxy-5-keto-d-gluconic acid (DKG); 2-deoxy-5-keto-d-gluconic acid 6-phosphate (DKGP); dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP); malonic semialdehyde (MSA). Adapted from Yoshida et al. (2008).

(DKGP). In the last reactions, the aldolase *IolJ* catalyses the cleavage of DKGP into dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP) and malonic semialdehyde (MSA), where DHAP is a common glycolytic intermediate, and MSA is converted to acetyl-CoA and CO₂ by a reaction catalysed by *IolA* (Anderson & Magasanik, 1971; Yoshida et al., 2008).

Thus, the complete catabolism of *myo*-inositol in *B. subtilis* (Figure 8) yields an equimolar mixture of DHAP, acetyl-CoA, and CO₂. All *iol* genes in *B. subtilis* are regulated by a single repressor encoded by the *iolR* gene; when *myo*-inositol is scarce

in the growth medium, the IolR repressor binds to operator site in the promoter region, ultimately repressing transcription of *iol* genes (Yoshida et al., 1999).

2.3.2 Enzymatic Properties of *Bacillus* Phytase

As phytases are enzymes, their catalytic activity is influenced by both pH and temperature. The majority of phytases derived from diverse *Bacillus* species exhibit comparable enzymatic characteristics, including similar molecular masses and optimal pH ranges; collectively, they are classified as BPPHys (T. Zhao et al., 2021). Of the previously described phytases common in fermented foods, the only class of phytase capable of retaining enzymatic activity under neutral or alkaline conditions is BPPhy (Chen et al., 2016; T. Zhao et al., 2021). According to the literature, BPPHys from *Bacillus* exhibits optimal activity within a pH range of 6.5–8.5, with minimal variation in specific activity across this interval. Furthermore, phytase expression increases markedly during the late stationary phase of growth (Choi et al., 2001; Pal Roy et al., 2017; Powar & Jagannathan, 1982; Shimizu, 1992). Additionally, BPPHys generally exhibits good thermal stability; for a BPPhy isolated from *B. licheniformis*, Tye et al. (2002) reported 80% enzymatic activity retained after heat treatment of 95 °C for 10 min.

The activity of *Bacillus* BPPhy is subject to regulation by several divalent metal ions. Notably, Ca^{2+} functions as an activator of BPPhy due to its role in maintaining conformational and catalytic activity, whereas Cd^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Fe^{2+} act as inhibitors (Reddy et al., 2015; T. Zhao et al., 2021). The inhibitory effect of these metal ions is attributable to their complexation with PA, resulting in the formation of a PA–mineral complex that exhibits reduced affinity for, and consequently suboptimal binding within, the active site of BPPHys. The importance of Ca^{2+} for the activity of *Bacillus* BPPhy was documented by Kerovuo et al. (2000), who reported a significant decrease in phytase activity after removal of Ca^{2+} from the enzyme solution. In addition, Choi et al. (2001) observed that the optimal pH range of *Bacillus* BPPHys expanded from 6.5–8.5 to 6.0–9.5 in the presence of 10 mM Ca^{2+} , accompanied by an enhancement in thermal stability. The effect of Ca^{2+} on *Bacillus* BPPhy was investigated by Oh et al. (2001), who reported a Ca^{2+} -dependent catalytic activity of the phytase by single point mutation experiments at sites Tyr159, Glu211, Glu260, and Asp314. This was confirmed by Shin et al. (2001), as a significant decrease in enzymatic activity was reported following mutation of the Ca^{2+} -chelating residues located in the active site.

2.3.3 Genetic Characteristics of *Bacillus* Phytase

In recent years, increasing attention has been directed toward studies investigating the sequence characteristics of *Bacillus* BPPhy, with the aim of elucidating species diversity as well as identifying key sites influencing enzymatic properties (T. Zhao et al.,

2021). A study performing *in silico* analysis of 44 *Bacillus* BPPHys protein sequences found conserved sites to be located in the N- and C-termini, with no cysteine residues present across the full-length sequences (V. Kumar et al., 2014). In the N-terminus, the NN[V/I]D[I/L/V]R[Y/D/Q] motif was present in all sequences following the conserved DA[A/T/E]DDPA[I/L/V]W motif; the valine residue in the NN[V/I]D[I/L/V]R[Y/D/Q] motif is proposed to participate in substrate binding during enzyme catalysis (V. Kumar et al., 2014). Additionally, V. Kumar et al. (2014) identified an aspartic acid residue located in the C-terminal region as being critical for the catalytic properties, as this acts as proton donor in the cleavage of phosphomonoester bond. Crystal structure analysis of *Bacillus* BPPHys showed a clear propeller structure composed of six anti-parallel β sheets, with a substrate binding pocket located in the N-terminus (Ha et al., 2000).

Figure 9: Interactions between PhoP and RNA polymerase (RNAP) in *Bacillus* in the absence (A) and presence (B) of phosphorylated PhoP (PhoP~P). In the absence of PhoP~P, RNAP is bound to the -35 promoter region of *phyC* facilitated by the σ^A factor. In the presence of PhoP~P, dimeric PhoP~P binds to the -35 promoter region and RNAP undergoes conformational changes that facilitates contact with the -10 promoter region, ultimately triggering transcription. Adapted from Makarewicz et al. (2006).

2.3.4 Regulatory Mechanism of *Bacillus* Phytase

The regulatory mechanisms of *Bacillus* BPPHy are well studied. In *Bacillus*, the *phyC* gene encodes the extracellular BPPHy, and at least two mechanisms are known to regulate *phyC* at a transcriptional level. First, the *Bacillus phyC* gene is a member of the P_i starvation-inducible Pho regulon of which the phosphorylated response regulator PhoP (PhoP~P) serves a dual role as both activator and repressor of *phyC* (Makarewicz et al., 2006). The promoter region of *phyC* contains two tandemly repeated PhoP TT[T/A/C]ACA binding boxes located within and upstream of the -35 consensus promoter region, as well as a single PhoP box in the -10 promoter region (Makarewicz et al., 2006). Dimeric PhoP~P activates *phyC* transcription upon binding to the -35 promoter region, whereas binding of PhoP~P to the -10 promoter region represses transcription. In the absence of PhoP~P, the RNA polymerase (RNAP) is bound to the -35 promoter region of *phyC* facilitated by the σ^A factor. Upon binding of the dimeric PhoP~P to the -35 promoter region, RNAP undergoes conformational changes that facilitates contact with the -10 promoter region, ultimately triggering transcription and preventing PhoP~P binding to the -10 promoter region (Makarewicz et al., 2006). As PhoP concentrations rise, the competition between PhoP~P and RNAP to the -10 promoter region increases, thus decreasing *phyC* transcription. An overview of the PhoP regulatory mechanism of *Bacillus phyC* is shown in Figure 9.

2.3.5 Secretion of *Bacillus* Phytase

Protein and enzyme secretion in *Bacillus* is dependent upon the presence of a specific signal peptide (SP) at the N-terminus of the protein sequence, which facilitates recognition by the cellular secretion machinery (Tjalsma et al., 2004; Tsuji et al., 2015). This pathway is also known as the Sec-dependent secretion pathway. In most cases, the SP constitutes a transient N-terminal extension that is cleaved by a specialized class of enzymes known as signal peptidases, once its targeting function has been fulfilled (von Heijne, 1990).

The study conducted by Tsuji et al. (2015) examined the influence of 173 distinct SPs on the secretion efficiency of phytases in *B. subtilis* when fused to the N-terminus of the target protein. The authors demonstrated that secretion efficiency was strongly dependent on the specific SP employed and concluded that, although gene expression may occur, efficient secretion is required for the strain to exhibit phytase activity.

2.4 Lactic Acid Bacteria in Fermented Foods

LAB has long been recognised to serve important functions in both food, agricultural and clinical applications. LAB are a non-phylogenetic group of bacteria, typically characterised as Gram-positive, non-spore-forming, non-respiring cocci or rods that produce

lactic acid as the primary end product of carbohydrate fermentation (Bintsis, 2018). Four main genera are generally considered to comprise LAB; *Lactobacillus*, *Leuconostoc*, *Pediococcus* and *Streptococcus*, but recent taxonomic revisions have proposed several new genera. The genus *Lactobacillus* has been reclassified into 23 novel genera, including *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* (Zheng et al., 2020). In relation to food fermentations, the importance of LAB is associated with their safe metabolic activity of utilising sugars to produce organic acids and other metabolites known to enhance flavour, texture, and nutritional value of fermented foods (Bintsis, 2018). As LAB are commonly found in fermented foods that have been consumed for centuries, they are naturally accepted as GRAS for human consumption (Ayivi et al., 2020).

LAB are capable of breaking down macromolecular compounds in foods, including the degradation of indigestible polysaccharides (Gänzle & Follador, 2012). At the same time, their metabolism leads to the production of a wide range of substances, such as short-chain fatty acids (Özcelik et al., 2016), amines (Barbieri et al., 2019), bacteriocins (Diep & Nes, 2002), vitamins (Capozzi et al., 2012; Taranto et al., 2003), and exopolysaccharides (Patel et al., 2012). Furthermore, LAB-mediated food fermentation has been demonstrated to effectively decrease PA content through hydrolytic processes (Fretzdorff & Brummer, 1992; Leenhardt et al., 2005; Lopez et al., 2000), an effect that is primarily attributed to the activity of endogenous phytases.

2.4.1 *myo*-Inositol Metabolism in Lactic Acid Bacteria

The compound *myo*-inositol is widely distributed across diverse environments, ranging from bacteria to fungi and higher plants, where it functions, among other roles, as an essential growth factor (Holub, 1986). Still, little knowledge on the biosynthesis and/or degradation of *myo*-inositol in *Limosilactobacillus* or *Lactiplantibacillus* have been obtained so far. Consequently, the phylogenetically closest organism with characterised *myo*-inositol metabolic pathways remains *Lacticaseibacillus casei*.

By performing a genome analysis of *Lacticaseibacillus casei* BL23, Yebra et al. (2007) documented the first example of an operon for *myo*-inositol utilisation in LAB, from which they discovered a DNA insertion containing all genes necessary for the catabolism of *myo*-inositol. Similar to *B. subtilis*, the operon consisted of an *iolR* gene encoding a transcriptional repressor, as well as the *iolTABCDGEJK* operon encoding a complete catabolic pathway of *myo*-inositol (Yebra et al., 2007). The authors report this to be in contrast with other *Lacticaseibacillus casei* strains unable to ferment *myo*-inositol. As for the previously described *myo*-inositol metabolism of *B. subtilis*, the pathways remains much the same in some *Lacticaseibacillus*. However, a key difference observed by Yebra et al. (2007) was the presence of the *iolK* gene, encoding a malonate semialdehyde decarboxylase. The authors ascribe the presence of *iolK* to the ability of some *Lacticas-*

Figure 10: *myo*-inositol catabolic pathways in *Lacticaseibacillus* including functions of *iol* genes. Abbreviations for metabolic intermediates: 2-keto-*myo*-inositol (2KMI); 3D-(3,5/4)-trihydroxycyclohexane-1,2-dione (THcHDO); 5-deoxy-d-glucuronic acid (5DG); 2-deoxy-5-keto-d-gluconic acid 6-phosphate (DKGP); dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP); malonic semialdehyde (MSA). Adapted from Yebra et al. (2007).

eibacillus species to metabolise malonic semialdehyde through two alternative pathways: 1) the classical *myo*-inositol catabolic pathway, in which IolA (malonate semialdehyde dehydrogenase) catalyses the conversion of malonic semialdehyde to acetyl-coenzyme A, and 2) an alternative route involving the conversion of malonic semialdehyde to acetaldehyde catalysed by the enzyme encoded by *iolK*. In the study by Yebra et al. (2007), transcriptional analyses revealed that the *iolTABCDGEJK* cluster was regulated through substrate-specific induction via inactivation of the transcriptional repressor IolR, as well as through carbon catabolite repression mediated by the transcriptional regulator catabolite control protein A (CcpA). An overview of the proposed *myo*-inositol catabolism in *Lacticaseibacillus* is shown in Figure 10.

2.4.2 Enzymatic Properties of Lactic Acid Bacteria Phytase

Although phytases primarily hydrolyse PA, some can also act on other phosphorylated substrates, including p-nitrophenyl phosphate, ATP, and various sugar phosphates to

facilitate the release of P_i (Vohra & Satyanarayana, 2003). Nevertheless, phytase activity is strongly influenced by substrate type. R. Sharma et al. (2018) characterised a PTPHy from *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* and reported significantly higher substrate specificity for PA than for α -D-glucose-1-phosphate or ATP. In contrast, Zamudio et al. (2001) reported that a PTPHy from *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* exhibited the lowest hydrolytic activity toward PA, attributing PA hydrolysis mainly to non-specific acid phosphatases. The differences in hydrolytic behaviour highlight that phytase activity is determined by enzyme origin as well as the chemical nature of the substrate.

Phytases derived from LAB generally exhibit maximal catalytic activity within a temperature range of 40–80 °C and an operational pH range of 4.0–7.5, although their responses to different mineral ions are highly variable (N. Sharma et al., 2020). R. Sharma et al. (2018) reported that the PTPHy from *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*, when heterologously expressed in *E. coli*, exhibited optimal activity at 60 °C and pH 5.0. Enzyme activity was further stimulated by Ag^+ , while Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , and F^- caused inhibition. In contrast, Ca^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Co^{2+} showed no measurable effect. Unlike most LAB phytases, which display optimal activity at moderate temperatures, Sumengen et al. (2013) reported that a phytase from *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* exhibited exceptionally high thermal stability, with maximal activity at 120 °C and an optimal pH of 3.4. Unlike some LAB phytases that are unaffected by metal ions, this enzyme was moderately inhibited by the presence of a broad range of divalent and trivalent ions, including Ca^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} .

2.4.3 Genetic Characteristics of Lactic Acid Bacteria Phytase

The available literature provides only limited information on the genetic characteristics of LAB phytases. A few studies have identified key catalytic residues and active sites based on the amino acid sequences; however, these investigations have been limited to individual strains.

The first and only genetically characterised PTPHy isolated from *Limosilactobacillus* was reported by R. Sharma et al. (2018). In their study, an active site within the PTP domain of the phytase, containing a conserved HCxxGxxRT motif, was identified. Comparison of the amino acid sequences revealed little similarity to PTPHy enzymes isolated from other Firmicutes, with only the active site and the PA-binding P-loop showing a high degree of conservation (R. Sharma et al., 2018). To date, a single study has reported on the isolation and genetic characterisation of a native *Lactiplantibacillus* phytase (Yang et al., 2022). In that work, the authors identified a highly active BPPHy, contradicting the general understating of PTPHy as the phytase type inherently associated with LAB. The authors reported that the amino acid sequence of the *Lactiplantibacillus* BPPHy showed high similarity to those of *B. amyloliquefaciens* and *B. subtilis*, including

comparable conserved active-site regions. Notably, the two presumed catalytical residues Glu146 and Glu195 were highly conserved among all three organisms (Yang et al., 2022). Considering the distinct differences between BPPHy and PTPHy, particularly in terms of their pH optima, and given that the genetic characterisation of LAB phytases has thus far been limited to individual strains, more comprehensive comparative studies are necessary to improve the current understanding of phytases inherent to LAB.

2.4.4 Regulatory Mechanisms of Lactic Acid Bacteria Phytase

Information on the regulatory mechanisms controlling phytase expression in LAB is extremely scarce. As a result, the available literature largely focuses on broader regulatory frameworks described for wider phylogenetic groups. Accordingly, the following section considers LAB in a general sense as representative.

For LAB, evidence suggests that phytase activity is not essential for balanced cellular growth but is instead synthesised in response to nutrient or energy limitation, thereby acting as an adaptive strategy to changing environmental conditions (Konietzny & Greiner, 2004). A central regulatory factor is P_i , which exerts strong repressive control over phytase formation in LAB (Konietzny & Greiner, 2004). High extracellular P_i concentrations typically inhibit phytase synthesis, whereas P_i -limiting conditions stimulate expression. This regulatory pattern implies that phytate degradation functions as a compensatory mechanism to liberate P_i under conditions of scarcity. In addition to P_i availability, the type and concentration of carbon sources significantly influence phytase production in LAB (Haros et al., 2008), highlighting the integration of phytase expression into broader carbon–phosphorus metabolic cross-regulation. Furthermore, phytase production has been observed in LAB during environmental adaptation prior to growth onset and under stress conditions in actively growing cells, suggesting a possible role in signal transduction or metabolic regulation beyond P_i acquisition (Haros et al., 2008).

For many years, no gene responsible for phytate degradation had been identified in LAB. However, recent advances have demonstrated the presence of a *phy* gene encoding a functional phytase in a single LAB species. In the study by R. Sharma et al. (2018), a novel *phyLf* gene encoding a PTPHy was identified in *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*, representing the first reported evidence of a phytase gene within the genus *Limosilactobacillus*. Despite these insights, the specific regulatory pathways coordinating phytase and other phosphatase genes, are poorly characterised (Molina et al., 2025).

2.4.5 Secretion of Lactic Acid Bacteria Phytase

Similar to *Bacillus*, many proteins and enzymes secreted by LAB are secreted via the Sec-dependent pathway, in which proteins are synthesized as precursor molecules containing an N-terminal SP that directs them to the Sec translocation machinery (Mathiesen et

al., 2009). However, to the best of current knowledge, the influence of specific SPs on the secretion efficiency of phytases in LAB has not been systematically described in the existing literature. Consequently, in order to fully exploit the potential of LAB as phytate-degrading microorganisms in plant-based proteinaceous foods, a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between specific SPs and phytase secretion efficiency is required.

3 Scope and Aim

This project reports on the PA-hydrolysing capabilities of food-grade bacteria belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus*. Genomic analyses were performed to identify enzymes and regulatory elements associated with phytase activity in bacteria, after which select candidates were subjected to experimental evaluation of phytase activity and their hydrolytic effects on PA in plant-based proteinaceous food prototypes.

The primary objective of this study was to assess the PA-hydrolysing capacity of strains within our bacterial collection in order to improve our understanding of phytase gene expression and the corresponding enzymatic activity. In doing so, this study aimed to address the existing knowledge gap concerning identification and genetic characterisation of phytase-encoding genes in LAB, whilst contributing to the establishment of fermentation as a viable and effective strategy for reducing PA concentrations in plant-based proteinaceous foods.

4 Materials and Methods

4.1 Whole Genome Sequencing of Bacterial Genomes

Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) was conducted on a collection of 64 bacterial strains prior to the extent of this project, and will therefore not be considered in the following results and discussion. Sequencing was conducted with Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) using native DNA as described in previous studies (Larsen et al., 2026; Soto-Serrano et al., 2024; Wiedenbein et al., 2023). Briefly, genomic DNA was extracted from bacterial cultures using the Bead-Beat Micro AX Gravity kit (cat. 106-100 M1; A&A Biotechnology, Gdynia, Poland), and sequencing was performed on ONT PromethION 2 Solo platform using R10.4.1 Flow cells in combination with MagAttract HMW DNA kit (Qiagen, Germantown, MD, USA). Genomes were assembled using Hybracter v0.11.2 (Bouras et al., 2024) using long-read format.

4.2 Phylogenetic Trees of Bacterial Core Genomes

The bacterial core genes are defined as single-copy, homologous genes that are present in most of the known bacterial species. Phylogenetic relationships of genomes from the bacterial collection were inferred by implementing the UBCG pipeline (Na et al., 2018), which constructs phylogenies based on a concatenated alignment of 92 conserved single-copy bacterial core genes. Genome assemblies in FASTA format were processed using the 'extract' module of UBCG to identify and retrieve orthologous core genes from each genome assembly. The extracted bacterial core gene files generated for all strains were subsequently used as input for multiple sequence alignment and concatenation. Alignments of the 92 conserved marker genes were generated using the 'align' module of the UBCG pipeline. The resulting concatenated multiple-sequence alignment was used for downstream maximum-likelihood phylogenetic reconstruction with FastTree (Price et al., 2010), and phylogenetic trees were visualised using iTOL (Letunic & Bork, 2024).

4.3 Identification of Target Phytase and Pho-Regulon Genes

Genomes were screened for phytase-encoding genes using the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) BLAST+ command-line suite (Camacho et al., 2008), employing tblastn searches in which each query protein sequence was aligned against the corresponding genome translated in all six reading frames. Alignments were scored with the BLOSUM62 substitution matrix, applying a gap-opening penalty of 11 and a gap-extension penalty of 1. For *Bacillus* strains, the query sequence was the BPPHy encoded by the *phyC* gene (GenBank: CAB91845.1), whereas for *Limosilactobacillus* strains, the PTPHy encoded by the *phyLf* gene (GenBank: AKS25181.2) was used as the query. For *Lactiplantibacillus* strains, the protein sequence of a recently characterised BPPHy (Yang et al., 2022) (GenBank: AVV65759.1) was used as the primary query, and in addition, the PTPHy encoded by *phyLf* from *Limosilactobacillus* was also searched against *Lactiplantibacillus* genomes.

A similar workflow was applied to identify genes belonging to the Pho-regulon, specifically those encoding the histidine kinase sensor protein (*phoR*) and the transcriptional response regulator (*phoP*). For *Bacillus* strains, the protein sequences of PhoR (GenBank: AEQ36701.1) and PhoP (GenBank: CAA47908.1) were used as query sequences. Corresponding PhoR and PhoP protein sequences from *Limosilactobacillus* (GenBank: SPE16890.1 and CAN3513202.1) and *Lactiplantibacillus* (GenBank: WPW64696.1 and CAN6956977.1) were likewise used as query sequences. Across all target gene identification analyses, significant hits were defined using a significance threshold of $E \leq 10^{-5}$.

4.4 Discovery of Putative PHO-Boxes

Putative PHO-Box elements within promoter regions of phytase-encoding genes were identified following procedures adapted from Corrales et al. (2025). Briefly, the core PHO-Box consensus previously characterised in *B. subtilis* (Eder et al., 1999; Qi et al., 1997) was used as a query to search for homologous sequences across all 64 bacterial genomes examined, given that *B. subtilis* is the most closely related organism to both *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* for which PHO-Boxes have been experimentally validated. 14 unique sequences were selected and used to infer a conserved motif using the GLAM2 algorithm (Frith et al., 2008) as implemented in MEME Suite (version 5.5.5). The resulting motif was then employed to systematically screen upstream genomic regions for candidate PHO-Boxes. The 14 sequences (Table S1) and the resulting motif inferred by the GLAM2 algorithm (Figure S1) is provided in Appendix 1.

Protein-coding genes were predicted from assembled but unannotated genomes of all 64 strains from the bacterial collection using Prodigal (Hyatt et al., 2010) in single-genome mode. Predicted gene coordinates were exported in GFF format and subsequently converted to BED format by extracting scaffold identifiers, start and end coordinates, and strand information. Genome indices were generated from the assembled FASTA file using SAMtools (H. Li et al., 2009), and scaffolds were retrieved from the resulting FASTA index file. Putative promoter-containing regions were defined as 300 bp upstream of the translational start site of each predicted gene and were extracted using BEDTools (Quinlan & Hall, 2010) with strand specificity enabled. Strand-corrected nucleotide sequences corresponding to these upstream regions were subsequently retrieved. Motif discovery was then performed with GLAM2Scan (MEME Suite) using the inferred conserved PHO-Box motif derived from *B. subtilis* as query. The extracted upstream sequences were systematically screened for occurrences of this motif and subsequently compared with the genomic positions of the corresponding phytase-encoding genes in each strain from the bacterial collection. Command line script employed for PHO-Box motif discovery analysis is provided in Appendix 2.

4.5 Multiple Sequence Alignment of Lactic Acid Bacteria Phytases

PTPhy protein sequences identified across the 58 bacterial strains of *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* were subjected to multiple sequence alignment using the Clustal Omega algorithm (Sievers & Higgins, 2021) as integrated in the 'msa' CRAN package (Bodenhofer et al., 2015). The input dataset comprised the protein sequences corresponding to the target genes previously identified through the established gene detection workflow. The resulting alignment of the PTPhy protein sequences, as well as its associated data, was subsequently visualised using the 'ggmsa' CRAN package (L. Zhou et al., 2022).

4.6 Pre-Cultivation of Selected Bacterial Strains

From the bacterial collection, 18 strains were selected as candidates based on diversity of core genomic characteristics, only including strains qualified as GRAS to support their applicability in food fermentations (Table 2). These strains were grown by streaking a freeze stock culture on agar plates (2% agar). Strains of *Bacillus* were grown on Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) agar (HiMedia, Germany), and strains of *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* were grown on Lactobacillus De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe (MRS) agar (HiMedia, Germany). Agar plates were incubated at 30 °C for 24 hours or until sufficient growth had occurred to allow for single colony isolation.

4.7 Initial Screening for Phytase-Producing Strains

4.7.1 Growth Medium

To evaluate the phytase activity of the selected bacterial strains, a screening approach was employed in which the ability of the organisms to grow with PA as the sole phosphorus

Table 2: List of bacteria selected for initial phytase screening assay based on maximising diversity of core genomes.

Genus	Species	Strain
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	Natto
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	PRO55
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	PRO93
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	PRO115
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	PRO120
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	PRO121
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	24-15
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	6h2cm1
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	L18
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	NSB8
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	UFLA CH 80
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	ZN1-10
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>argentoratensis</i>	10-15B
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>argentoratensis</i>	10-9B
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>plantarum</i>	0h1s1
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>plantarum</i>	2-1
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>plantarum</i>	36h8h1
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>plantarum</i>	UFLA SAY 96

source was assessed. For this, a phytase screening medium (PSM) composed of glucose (20 g/L), phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (P8810; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany) (4 g/L), calcium chloride dihydrate (2 g/L), ammonium nitrate (5 g/L), potassium chloride (0.5 g/L), magnesium sulphate heptahydrate (0.5 g/L), iron sulphate heptahydrate (0.01 g/L) and manganese sulphate monohydrate (0.01 g/L) and 2% agar was made. As positive control, a similar agar medium was made with potassium dihydrogen phosphate (2 g/L) as substitute to phytic acid sodium salt hydrate, thereby making phosphorus freely available in the medium. The heat-sensitive phytic acid sodium salt hydrate was added after autoclaving, by filtering through 0.22 μm Q-Max filters (Mikrolab Frisenette, Denmark). Both PSM agar and the positive control agar were adjusted to pH 5.5.

4.7.2 Phytase Plate Screening Assay

From the pre-cultivated bacteria, an overnight culture was prepared for each strain by inoculating a single colony into 10 mL of corresponding broth medium (BHI for *Bacillus* or MRS for LAB). Overnight cultures of *Bacillus* strains were incubated at 37 °C for 18 hours with agitation at 200 rpm, and overnight cultures of *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* strains were incubated at 30° C for 18 hours with no agitation. After incubation, the cultures were centrifuged (10.000 \times g for 10 minutes) and resuspended in 0.9% (w/v) NaCl solution before adjusted to OD₆₀₀ = 0.1 (0.9% (w/v) NaCl solution was used as blank). From each of the OD-adjusted bacterial suspensions, three technical replicates of 10 μL was propagated on PSM and positive controls agar plates and subsequently incubated at 30 °C for 96 hours. Each strain was cultured in duplicates.

4.7.3 Assessment of Phytase-Producing Strains

Strains capable of hydrolysing PA were assessed based on methodology described by Nguyen et al. (1992) as used in the study by El Ifa et al. (2024). Briefly, phytase-producing strains were identified by the appearance of a clear visible halo zone, and the solubilising efficiency was calculated as

$$SE = \frac{D_H}{D_G} \cdot 100$$

where SE is the solubilising efficiency (%), D_H is the diameter of the clear halo zone (mm), and D_G is the diameter of the bacterial growth zone (mm).

4.7.4 Analysis of Results

To evaluate the phytase-producing capabilities statistically, samples were categorised by strain identity, with each group consisting of two biological replicates each representing the mean of the three technical replicates. Differences between strains were examined us-

ing one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), in which SE (%) was treated as the continuous dependent variable and strain as the independent factor. Significant overall differences were assessed by conducting Tukey’s Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc test for pairwise comparisons, using a significance threshold of $p \leq 0.05$.

4.8 Phytase Activity

4.8.1 Bacterial Strains and Growth in Liquid Phytase Screening Medium

From the initial screening of phytase-producing strains, two strains from each genus (*Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus*) were selected for further analysis (Table 3). Overnight cultures were prepared for each strain according to phytase plate screening assay procedures. After incubation, overnight cultures were centrifuged ($10.000 \times g$ for 10 minutes), supernatants were discarded, and the pellets were resuspended in 0.9% (w/v) NaCl to serve as inoculum. Samples for each strain was prepared in glass tubes containing 10 mL of PSM broth adjusted to pH 7.0 for *Bacillus* and pH 5.5 for LAB. Inoculation level was set to 5% (500 μ L inoculum into 10 mL PSM broth). PSM broth inoculated with *Bacillus* were incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours with agitation at 200 rpm, and PSM broth inoculated with LAB were incubated at 30 °C for 48 hours with no agitation. Each strain was cultured in triplicates.

Table 3: List of bacteria selected for phytase activity assay based on initial screening procedures.

Genus	Species	Strain
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	Natto
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i>	PRO55
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	24-15
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i>	NSB8
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>argentoratensis</i>	10-9B
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>plantarum</i>	36h8h1

4.8.2 Extraction of Phytases

After incubation, extracellular phytases were extracted by centrifugation ($10.000 \times g$ for 10 minutes, 4 °C). Supernatants were collected, filtered using 0.22 μ m Q-Max filters (Mikrolab Frisenette, Denmark) and kept on ice until activity assay was carried out.

Intracellular phytases were extracted by resuspending the remaining pellets in sodium acetate buffer (0.2 M sodium acetate/HCl buffer, pH 5.5) before transferring the suspensions to Bead-Beater Tubes (A&A Biotechnology, Poland) containing a mixture of 0.1 and

1 mm zirconia/silica beads. Samples were disrupted/homogenised using a FastPrep®-24 5G Bead Beating Grinder and Lysis System (MP Biomedicals, USA) running 3 cycles of 20 seconds at 6 m/s with a 3 minute rest period on ice between cycles. Samples were subsequently centrifuged ($10.000 \times g$ for 15 minutes, 4 °C), supernatants were collected, filtered using 0.22 μm Q-Max filters (Mikrolab Frisenette, Denmark) and kept on ice until activity assay was carried out.

4.8.3 Determination of Phytase Activity

Phytase activity was assayed as described by Nuobariene et al. (2011) with minor adjusting: 400 μL of phytic acid sodium salt hydrate solution (3 mM phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (P8810; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany) in 0.2 M sodium acetate/HCl buffer, pH 5.5) was pre-incubated at 30 °C for 5 minutes before adding 100 μL of enzyme extract and mixing thoroughly. Samples were incubated at 30 °C for 20 minutes before stopping the reaction by adding 500 μL of 10% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid (TCA). For each sample, a control was prepared by substituting phytic acid sodium salt hydrate solution with sodium acetate buffer, otherwise measured under identical conditions. A negative control sample with no added enzyme extract was included in the assay.

Measurement of P_i hydrolysed from PA was performed based on methodology developed by Heinonen and Lahti (1981) as used in the study by Nuobariene et al. (2011): 100 μL of assay sample was mixed with 800 μL of acid molybdate colour reagent (1 volume of 10 mM ammonium molybdate, 1 volume of 2.5 M sulfuric acid, 2 volume of acetone), and the resulting yellow colour was measured at 355 nm using a Genesys 180 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). Blank was prepared by combining 400 μL sodium acetate buffer with 500 μL TCA.

A standard curve for phosphate was prepared using a potassium phosphate stock solution (2 mM potassium phosphate monobasic (P0662; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany) in 0.2 M sodium acetate/HCl buffer, pH 5.5) and measured under conditions identical to assay samples. Volumetric activities of both extracellular and intracellular phytases were calculated as

$$U \text{ mL}^{-1} = \frac{\Delta c_{PO_4}}{\Delta t} \cdot \frac{V_t}{V}$$

where V is the volume of enzyme extract (mL), V_t is the total sample volume (mL), Δt is the reaction time (minutes) and Δc_{PO_4} is the measured change in P_i concentration ($\mu\text{mol mL}^{-1}$).

4.8.4 Analysis of Results

For the statistical assessment of phytase activity, samples were categorised by strain identity, with each group consisting of three biological replicates. Extracellular and in-

tracellular phytase activities were evaluated separately. Differences between strains were examined using one-way ANOVA, in which phytase activity ($U \text{ mL}^{-1}$) served as the continuous dependent variable and strain as the independent factor. Distinct ANOVA models were constructed for the extracellular and intracellular datasets. Significant overall differences were assessed by conducting Tukey’s HSD post hoc test for pairwise comparisons, using a significance threshold of $p \leq 0.05$.

4.9 Faba Bean Fermentations

4.9.1 Faba Bean Liquid Growth Medium

To evaluate select candidate’s ability to hydrolyse PA in a proteinaceous plant-based food prototype, a faba bean medium (FBM) was prepared. For this purpose, Danish faba beans purchased from Biogan (Lystrup, Denmark) were milled and sieved using a 0.5 mm mesh. The resulting powder was subsequently sterilised by γ -irradiation, performed by STERIS (Ohio, USA).

4.9.2 Bacterial Strains and Fermentation of Faba Bean Medium

On the basis of the results obtained from the preliminary screening for phytase-producing strains, followed by the quantitative determination of phytase activity, *B. subtilis* Natto and PRO55 were identified as the top-performing candidates for subsequent evaluation in FBM. In addition, *B. subtilis* PRO120 was included as a negative control strain. Overnight cultures of all strains were prepared as previously described for the phytase plate screening assay. After incubation, overnight cultures were centrifuged ($10.000 \times g$ for 10 minutes), the resulting supernatants were discarded, and the cell pellets were resuspended in 0.9% (w/v) NaCl solution to be used as inoculum. Samples for each strain was prepared in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 100 mL of 10% (w/v) FBM. Inoculation level was set to 1% (1 mL inoculum into 100 mL FBM). Following inoculation, samples were incubated at 30 °C for 48 hours with agitation at 120 rpm. Uninoculated control samples at 0 and 48 hours were included in the experiment. After incubation, samples were lyophilised for 48 hours at 0.04 mbar and subsequently ground into fine particulates using a ceramic mortar.

4.9.3 Quantification of Phytic Acid

PA content was quantified using the Phytic Acid Assay Kit (K-PHYT; Megazyme, Ireland) in accordance with the manufacturer’s protocol. In brief, 50 mg of sample were extracted in 1 mL of hydrochloric acid (0.66 M) under continuous stirring for 3 hours. The extracts were then centrifuged ($15.000 \times g$ for 10 minutes) and 0.5 mL of the supernatant was neutralised with sodium hydroxide (0.75 M). Subsequently, 50 μL of the neutralised

extract was incubated with phytase and alkaline phosphatase at 40 °C. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 50% (w/v) TCA, and the absorbance was measured at 655 nm using a Genesys 180 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). For each sample, three technical replicates were assayed for quantification of PA.

4.9.4 Analysis of Results

For the statistical assessment of PA hydrolysis in FBM, samples were categorised by strain identity, with each group consisting of three technical replicates. Differences between strains were examined using one-way ANOVA, in which PA content ($\text{g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) served as the continuous dependent variable and strain as the independent factor. Significant overall differences were assessed by conducting Tukey's HSD post hoc test for pairwise comparisons, using a significance threshold of $p \leq 0.05$.

4.10 Phytase Gene Expression Analysis (Preparation Only)

4.10.1 Selection of Target Sequences for qPCR and Primer Design

For future RT-qPCR analysis, two reference genes were chosen for each genus. For *Bacillus* strains, *ssbA* (single-strand DNA-binding protein, GenBank: NP_391970.1) and *gyrB* (DNA gyrase subunit B, GenBank: SNY80282.1) were selected following recent validation by Nuwong and Kittiwongwattana (2022). For *Limosilactobacillus* strains, *dnaG* (DNA primase, GenBank: CAJ1221591.1) and *gapA* (glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, GenBank: SNX31053.1) were chosen based on their reported stability (Kong et al., 2026; W. Zhao et al., 2011). Homologues genes were used for *Lactiplantibacillus* strains, as *dnaG* (DNA primase, GenBank: VDH12078.1) and *gapA* (glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, GenBank: BBM20962.1) were selected as reference genes.

Primer pairs specific to the phytase genes and selected reference genes were designed using Primer-BLAST (Ye et al., 2012). This tool integrates Primer3 (Koressaar & Remm, 2007; Kõressaar et al., 2018; Untergasser et al., 2012) for primer design with BLAST-based specificity screening. The PCR amplicon size was restricted to 100-200 nucleotides, and primer GC content was set between 40-60%. Maximum self-complementarity and pair-complementarity were limited to four nucleotides to reduce the likelihood of primer-dimer formation and intramolecular hairpin structures. The melting temperature (T_m) of each primer was constrained to a range of 57-63 °C, with a maximum allowable difference of 3 °C between forward and reverse primers. Primers selected for future phytase gene expression experiments is listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Primers prepared for future phytase gene expression analysis experiment. Two sets of primers were designed for each gene.

Gene	Primer	Sequence (5' to 3')	T _m (°C)	Product size (bp)
<i>Bacillus</i>				
<i>phyC</i>	F1	GGCCTGGTTGCAGATGATGAA	61.0	128
	R1	TGATCGCCTGTTGCTCTATCA	59.2	
	F2	TTACAGCACATACAGAAACAGATCC	59.1	149
	R2	GCCATCCAGATCATACAACACCA	59.1	
<i>ssbA</i>	F1	CAGGCGTTGATGGCAGACT	60.4	104
	R1	CGGTTCCAGAAATTGAACTGATTCT	59.8	
	F2	CCGGAAGTGAAGATATACACCGAAT	60.0	102
	R2	AAAATCTGCTTCTCTTTTCGCCTG	59.8	
<i>gyrB</i>	F1	CGTTGGCGCATCAGTTGTTA	59.5	107
	R1	CTGTAACCGGAACGCCTCTT	60.0	
	F2	TGCAGATGTTGATGGCGCA	60.7	107
	R2	GCGGCGGTTGTGCAATATAAA	60.2	
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>				
<i>phyLf</i>	F1	TCGTGTTCCACATACAGCTACA	59.4	126
	R1	TGACGAGCACCTGAAACTGG	60.3	
	F2	CGTGCTGGTGCTTTAGGTCA	60.6	132
	R2	AGCTGTATGTGGAAGTAGCATCA	59.8	
<i>gapA</i>	F1	GCGTAATAATCGTACAGCTTCAACA	60.0	137
	R1	ATGAACCATCAACAACACCAACAC	60.4	
	F2	TGCGTAATAATCGTACAGCTTCAAC	60.0	139
	R2	AATGAACCATCAACAACACCAACAC	60.9	
<i>dnaG</i>	F1	TGGTGTTCGTTTCAGGTATTGCT	60.2	123
	R1	GCATTTTGACCAGCAGCATCA	60.1	
	F2	AGGTCAAGTTCAAGAATTAGCTGC	59.5	126
	R2	GCTGTTGTTGTTGTTGGTGGT	60.1	
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>				
<i>phyLp</i>	F1	TGCTATGGCTGAAGCTCGTG	60.5	97
	R1	AGCAGCATCTAAATAAGCAGCA	58.5	
	F2	GGTGCTATGGCTGAAGCTCG	61.2	98
	R2	GCAGCATCTAAATAAGCAGCATC	58.5	
<i>gapA</i>	F1	GTCCAGTTCGTGGTGGTTAATTTT	59.4	140
	R1	AACACGTTGAGCATGACCTTGAA	61.2	
	F2	TCCAGTTCGTGGTGGTTAATTTTC	59.2	139
	R2	AACACGTTGAGCATGACCTTGTAAT	61.5	
<i>dnaG</i>	F1	CCACCACCAGCTACAGTTGA	59.6	129
	R1	AGCAATAGCCATAACACGTAACC	59.1	
	F2	GGTGTGCTTCAATGGGTACAT	59.2	118
	R2	GATCTGTAGCTTTTGACCTGGC	59.9	

5 Results

5.1 Whole Genome Sequence-Based Phylogeny

Phylogenetic relationships among the investigated bacterial strains were inferred based on concatenated alignments of 92 conserved bacterial core genes. Separate maximum-likelihood phylogenetic trees were constructed for the genera *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus*, and *Lactiplantibacillus* (Figure 11). Minor differences in tree scales among datasets reflected variation in the overall levels of sequence divergence.

The *Bacillus* phylogeny revealed a comparatively simple topology, characterised by short branch lengths. *B. subtilis* strains PRO120 and PRO121 formed a closely related subcluster, and PRO55 and PRO115 likewise grouped together with high genetic similarity. The *B. subtilis* Natto strain clustered more closely with the PRO55/PRO115 lineage than with the PRO120/PRO121 group. In contrast, PRO93 formed a distinct branch, displaying higher degree of phylogenetic divergence relative to the remaining isolates.

Phylogeny of *Limosilactobacillus* demonstrated clear clustering of the investigated strains into several distinct clades. Closely related isolates, including *Ll. fermentum* strains 20-8 and 24-15, together with strains ZN1-10, ZN6-9, and ZN2-6, formed compact subclusters characterised by short branch lengths, suggesting a high level of genomic relatedness. Furthermore, the *Ll. fermentum* UFLA CH strains grouped within a strongly supported lineage, further indicating close evolutionary relationships among these.

Phylogenetic analysis of the genus *Lactiplantibacillus* separated the isolates into two principal clades corresponding to *Lp. plantarum* and *Lp. argentoratensis*. The *Lp. plantarum* strains formed several closely related subclusters, including the UFLA CH isolates and strains RTIX-727 and RTVIII-721, indicating a high degree of genomic similarity. In contrast, the *Lp. argentoratensis* isolates grouped within a distinct and more divergent lineage, in which strains s5, 10-15B, and 12-27B formed a separate cluster that was clearly differentiated from the remaining isolates.

5.2 *In Silico* Analysis of Phytase and Pho-Regulon Genes

To identify phytase genes present in bacteria from the strain collection, each genome was screened for phytase-encoding sequences by aligning a reference phytase protein against dynamically translated genomic sequences in the six possible reading frames. A single copy of the BPPhy-encoding gene, *phyC*, was identified in all six examined *Bacillus* strains, whereas a single copy of the PTPhy-encoding gene, *phyLf*, was detected in each of the 26 analysed *Limosilactobacillus* strains. In contrast, screening for the BPPhy-encoding gene previously reported in *Lactiplantibacillus* by Yang et al. (2022) did not yield any significant sequence matches among the 32 *Lactiplantibacillus* strains from the bacterial collection. Instead, single-copy homologues of the PTPhy-encoding gene,

Figure 11: Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic trees of bacterial strains belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus*. Annotation columns show presence (fill) or absence (empty) of genetic elements involved in phytase gene expression. Select 18 candidates are highlighted in red.

phyLf, were identified in all examined *Lactiplantibacillus* strains. For the purposes of the present study, this newly identified PTPHy-encoding gene in *Lactiplantibacillus* is hereafter designated *phyLp*.

Using an approach similar to that employed for the identification of phytase-encoding genes, the analysis of Pho-regulon associated genes revealed the presence of a single copy of both the histidine kinase sensor gene (*phoR*) and the response regulator gene (*phoP*) in all 64 strains within the bacterial collection. A summary of the distribution of specific phytase and Pho-regulon genes is presented in Figure 11.

5.3 *In Silico* Analysis of Putative PHO-Boxes

The identification of putative PHO-Box elements across all 64 genomes in the bacterial collection was performed by screening for sequences homologous to the experimentally validated PHO-Box consensus motif of *B. subtilis*. Motif discovery analysis did not reveal any matches within the upstream regions of phytase-encoding genes in the examined strains of *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus*, or *Lactiplantibacillus*. A summary of the presence or absence of PHO-Box elements across the bacterial collection is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 12: Display of a segment from the multiple sequence alignment of protein tyrosine phosphatase-like phytase amino acid sequences identified in strains of *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* from the bacterial collection. The conserved HCxxGxxRT motif is highlighted in red within the consensus sequence.

5.4 Lactic Acid Bacteria Phytase Sequence Analysis

To further assess the newly identified PTPHy-encoding gene, *phyLp*, in *Lactiplantibacillus* using *in silico* approaches, multiple sequence alignment was performed for all identified PTPHy protein sequences. The alignment revealed that sequence variability was greatest at the inter-generic level, with additional species-specific variation observed between *Lp. plantarum* and *Lp. argenteratensis*. Notably, a conserved region present in all 58 strains of *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* contained the HCxxGxxRT motif associated with the active site within the PTP domain of PTPHy (Figure 12).

5.5 Screening for Phytase-Producing Strains

From the bacterial collection, 18 strains were selected with the aim of maximising core genome diversity (Figure 11) after which they were evaluated for their phytase-producing

Table 5: Solubilising efficiency (*SE*) of bacterial strains selected from genomic analysis. Letters indicate significant differences identified from one-way ANOVA following Tukey’s HSD post hoc test ($p \leq 0.05$).

Genus	Species and strain	<i>SE</i> \pm standard deviation (%)	Positive control agar growth
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>subtilis</i> Natto	149 \pm 9 ^b	Yes
	<i>subtilis</i> PRO55	219 \pm 61 ^a	Yes
	<i>subtilis</i> PRO93	No growth	Yes
	<i>subtilis</i> PRO115	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>subtilis</i> PRO120	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>subtilis</i> PRO121	No growth	Yes
<i>Lactiplantibacillus</i>	<i>argenteratensis</i> 10-15B	65 \pm 2 ^c	Yes
	<i>argenteratensis</i> 10-9B	85 \pm 2 ^c	Yes
	<i>plantarum</i> 0h1s1	57 \pm 2 ^{cd}	Yes
	<i>plantarum</i> 2-1	54 \pm 1 ^{cd}	Yes
	<i>plantarum</i> 36h8h1	83 \pm 2 ^c	Yes
	<i>plantarum</i> UFLA_SAY_96	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
<i>Limosilactobacillus</i>	<i>fermentum</i> 24-15	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>fermentum</i> 6h2cm1	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>fermentum</i> L18	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>fermentum</i> NSB8	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>fermentum</i> UFLA_CH_80	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes
	<i>fermentum</i> ZN1-10	0 \pm 0 ^d	Yes

capabilities. Among these, seven strains exhibited halo zones of clearing either within or surrounding their respective growth zone. The solubilising efficiency (SE), calculated based on the ratio between halo and growth zones, was highest for two strains of *B. subtilis*; namely PRO55 ($SE = 219 \pm 61\%$) and Natto ($SE = 149 \pm 9\%$), both showing significantly higher SE compared to the remaining strains. Among the *Lactiplantibacillus* strains, five produced detectable halo zones of clearing. Notably, *Lp. argentoratensis* 10-15B ($SE = 65 \pm 2\%$), *Lp. argentoratensis* 10-9B ($SE = 85 \pm 2\%$) and *Lp. plantarum* 36h8h1 ($SE = 83 \pm 2\%$) demonstrated significantly higher SE compared to the remaining strains, with the exception of *B. subtilis* PRO55 and Natto. None of the *Limosilactobacillus* strains formed a detectable halo zone of clearing under the assay conditions. All strains exhibited growth on the positive control agar plates, where phosphate was readily available in the medium. A summary of results from the screening of phytase-producing strains is presented in Table 5.

5.6 Quantification of Phytase Activities

Based on the outcomes of the screening for phytase-producing strains, six strains were selected for subsequent quantitative assessment of both extracellular and intracellular

Figure 13: Volumetric extracellular (A) and intracellular (B) phytase activities (mU ml⁻¹) of select bacterial strains. Letters indicate significant differences identified from one-way ANOVA following Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($p \leq 0.05$).

phytase activities. Two *Bacillus* strains (PRO55 and Natto) and two *Lactiplantibacillus* strains (10-9B and 36h8h1) were selected as representative strains due to their high *SE* values. In addition, two *Limosilactobacillus* strains (24-15 and NSB8) were included on an arbitrary basis, as none of the strains within this genus demonstrated phytase-producing capability in the initial screening assay.

After the 48 hours of incubation, all cultures demonstrated detectable microbial growth indicated by increased turbidity of the growth medium. Volumetric extracellular phytase activities ranged from 120.1 to 170.7 mU mL⁻¹, whereas volumetric intracellular phytase activities ranged from 148.8 to 163.2 mU mL⁻¹. No statistically significant differences were detected among the selected strains with respect to either extracellular or intracellular volumetric phytase activity (Figure 13). Unexpectedly, under the applied assay conditions, the negative control exhibited volumetric phytase activities that were statistically indistinguishable from those measured in both the extracellular and intracellular fractions.

5.7 Diagnostic Evaluation and Optimisation of Phytase Activity Assay

Prior to the determination of phytase activity as presented above, enzymatic activity was initially evaluated using the Phytase Assay Kit (K-PHYTASE; Megazyme, Ireland), following the manufacturer's instructions. For this preliminary assessment, strains of *B. subtilis* were selected as phytase-producing candidates. Under these assay conditions, no detectable phytase activity was observed, thereby necessitating the implementation of a systematic troubleshooting strategy. The following section provides a chronological account of the successive modifications introduced into the assay protocol, together with the principal observations obtained at each iteration. A summary of the resulting data is presented in Appendix 3 (Table S2), and a flow diagram outlining the successive modifications is presented in Appendix 4 (Figure S2).

Unadjusted K-PHYTASE Assay Overnight cultures were prepared by inoculating single colonies into liquid BHI medium, followed by 1% (v/v) inoculation into liquid PSM medium (pH 5.5) supplemented with phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (P8810; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany). Cultures were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours with agitation at 200 rpm. Extracellular phytase was collected from the culture supernatant, and intracellular phytase was extracted using sodium acetate buffer (0.25 M, pH 5.5, containing 0.01% polysorbate 20). Enzymatic assays were conducted for 20 min at 40 °C in the sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.5). No detectable enzymatic activity was observed following the application of these procedures.

Optimum β -Propeller Phytase Conditions Overnight cultures, PSM inoculations, and phytase extractions were carried out as previously described. To ensure conditions considered optimal for *Bacillus* BPPHy, enzymatic assays were carried out for 20 min at 55 °C in sodium acetate buffer adjusted to pH 7.0. Additionally, a parallel assay was performed using a preparation supplemented with 5 mM CaCl₂. No detectable enzymatic activity was observed following the application of these procedures.

Optimised Growth Conditions (V1) Overnight cultures were prepared as previously described. Subsequently, 1% (v/v) inoculations were made into liquid PSM medium (pH 7.0) supplemented with phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (P8810; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany). Only extracellular phytase activity was analysed. Assays were performed for 20 min at 40 °C in Tris buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.0, containing 0.01% polysorbate 20). No detectable enzymatic activity was observed following the application of these procedures.

Optimised Growth Conditions (V2) Overnight cultures were prepared as in previous experiments. Prior to PSM inoculation, cells were washed in 0.9% (w/v) NaCl, and 1% (v/v) inoculations were then transferred into liquid PSM medium (pH 7.0) supplemented with phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (P8810; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany). Cultures were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours with agitation at 200 rpm, after which a second round of PSM inoculations was performed following the same procedure. Enzymatic assays were conducted for 20 min at 40 °C in sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.5). No detectable enzymatic activity was observed following the application of these procedures.

New Phytic Acid Source Overnight cultures were prepared as previously described. Prior to PSM inoculation, cells were washed in 0.9% (w/v) NaCl. From these, 1% and 3% (v/v) inoculations were made into liquid PSM medium (pH 6.0) supplemented with phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (68388; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany). Cultures were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours with agitation at 200 rpm. Only extracellular phytase was collected and assayed. Enzymatic assays were carried out for 20 min at 40 °C in sodium acetate buffer adjusted to pH 6.0. No detectable enzymatic activity was observed following the application of these procedures.

5.8 Fermentation of Faba Bean Medium

Two strains of *B. subtilis* (Natto and PRO55) were selected as candidates for the evaluation of PA hydrolysis in FBM; a proteinaceous plant-based food prototype. In addition, *B. subtilis* PRO120 was included as a negative control strain. After 48 hours of fermentation, the PA content in the fermented FBM ranged from 0.85 to 1.88 g 100 g⁻¹. Fermentation

with both *B. subtilis* Natto and PRO55 resulted in significantly lower PA levels compared with those observed in *B. subtilis* PRO120 and the uninoculated 0-hour control (Figure 14). Unexpectedly, the 48-hour uninoculated control did not differ significantly from the other treatment groups.

Figure 14: Phytic acid content (g 100 g⁻¹) in faba bean medium following fermentation with selected *B. subtilis* strains, including 0- and 48-hour uninoculated controls. Letters indicate significant differences identified from one-way ANOVA following Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($p \leq 0.05$).

6 Discussion

6.1 *In Silico* Phytase Gene Identification

Several previous studies have identified the BPPhy-encoding gene, *phyC*, in various *Bacillus* species, including *B. subtilis* (Choi et al., 2001; Ha et al., 2000; Kerovuo et al., 1998; Kim et al., 1998; Powar & Jagannathan, 1982; Reddy et al., 2015; Shimizu, 1992). The findings of the present study, demonstrating the presence of *phyC* in all examined *Bacillus* strains, are therefore in accordance with and further supports the existing literature on BPPhy in *Bacillus*. To date, the study by R. Sharma et al. (2018) remains the only published work reporting the identification of the PTPhy-encoding gene, *phyLf*, in members of *Limosilactobacillus*. The detection of *phyLf* in all examined *Limosilactobacillus* strains in the present study thus further corroborates the findings reported by R. Sharma et al. (2018).

The present work reports on the first identification of the PTPHy-encoding gene, *phyLp*, in members of *Lactiplantibacillus*. These findings contradict those of Yang et al. (2022), who reported the presence of a BPPHy-encoding gene in *Lactiplantibacillus*. The authors report that the amino acid sequence of the identified BPPHy exhibits high similarity to those encoded by *phyC* in *Bacillus*, including conservation of all active-site residues. However, given the alkaline activity profile of BPPHys, which exhibits maximal enzymatic activity within a pH range of 6.5–7.5 (Greiner & Konietzny, 2006), it appears unlikely that the occurrence of a BPPHy in *Lactiplantibacillus* can be regarded as a generally valid phenomenon. To further elucidate phytases endogenous to *Lactiplantibacillus*, a comprehensive investigation encompassing a large collection of bacterial strains should be conducted to establish correlations between *in silico* genetic characterisation, *in vitro* confirmation of enzymatic activity, and *in vivo* phytase gene expression profiles.

6.2 *In Silico* PHO-Box Discovery

When searching for motifs homologous to the experimentally validated PHO-Box consensus motif from *B. subtilis*, no matches were identified within upstream regions of phytase-encoding genes in any of the examined strains of *Bacillus*, *Limosilactobacillus*, or *Lactiplantibacillus*. Similar observations were reported by Corrales et al. (2025), who likewise failed to detect PHO-Box motif matches in upstream regions of phytase-encoding genes in *Lactiacaseibacillus paracasei* (a LAB in which phytase production has previously been reported (Bhagat et al., 2019)) when applying an identical motif discovery strategy.

The findings of the present study suggests that, since PHO-Box motifs exhibit inter-species variability (Blanco et al., 2002), the PHO-Box consensus motif defined for *B. subtilis* cannot be regarded as optimal for robust motif detection across distinct taxonomic classes. Nonetheless, given that *B. subtilis* is currently the phylogenetically closest organism to both *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* for which PHO-Boxes have been experimentally validated, its use remains the most appropriate approach at present. To enable more accurate *in silico* identification of PHO-Box motifs in LAB, future studies should focus on the species-specific experimental validation of the regulatory role of PhoP in pho-regulon gene expression, in addition to genetic characterisation of the corresponding upstream regions and the associated DNA:PhoP molecular interactions.

When considering a possible explanation for the absence of PHO-Box motifs in the upstream regions of *phyC* in the examined strains of *Bacillus*, it should be noted that several well-characterised members of the Pho regulon have been reported to lack recognisable conserved PHO-Box motifs (Allenby et al., 2012; Martín et al., 2012). It should also be taken into account that, if the phytase-encoding gene is embedded within a larger operon, such an arrangement would not have been detected using the described methodology. Therefore, a clear explanation to these observations is still lacking.

6.3 Sequence Analysis of Putative *Lactiplantibacillus* Phytase

The alignment of PTPhy protein sequences identified in strains of *Limosilactobacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* revealed a highly conserved region containing the conserved HCxxGxxRT motif. This work presents the first genetic characterisation of PTPhy from *Lactiplantibacillus*. Given that conserved regions of proteins highlight areas of evolutionary, functional or structural importance (Orengo et al., 2003; Tsai & Chiu, 2008), the findings of the present study suggest that the newly identified *phyLp* in *Lactiplantibacillus* is likely to possess a functional role.

6.4 Phytase Activity Analyses

In the present study, none of the examined *Limosilactobacillus* strains exhibited phytase-producing capabilities during the initial screening procedures. This observation is consistent with the findings reported by Jo et al. (2021), in which strains of *Ll. fermentum* generally showed no detectable phytase activity when cultivated in rice medium, MRS, or a PA-based medium comparable to the PSM employed in the present study. Although phytase-encoding genes were identified in all examined strains, the lack of phytase-producing capabilities may be attributed to limited gene expression or inefficient enzyme secretion; both of which have been highlighted as prerequisites for effective PA hydrolysis by Tsuji et al. (2015). Consequently, future research should aim to elucidate the relationship between phytase gene expression and enzyme secretion efficiency in order to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing bacterial phytase activity.

In the study conducted by Madsen et al. (2019), various substrates were evaluated for use in phytase activity assays, and substantially increased assay absorbance was observed when phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (P8810; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany) was employed as the PA source. Based on these findings, the authors concluded that P8810 exhibits greater susceptibility to hydrolysis in comparison to similar alternatives. A plausible explanation for the lack of detectable phytase activity observed in the present study is that the use of P8810 in the preparation of the PSM may have resulted in the presence of P_i , thereby repressing the expression of phytase-encoding genes. However, upon substituting P8810 with phytic acid sodium salt hydrate (68388; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany) in the preparation of the PSM, still no detectable enzymatic activity was observed. Consequently, the underlying cause of lacking phytase activity under the applied assay conditions remains unresolved. For future analyses, the implementation of an appropriate alternative to P8810 should be considered to enable an unbiased quantification of enzymatic activity. In addition, the use of a more nutrient-rich, chemically defined growth medium should be considered, as the relatively minimal composition of PSM may have imposed an additional repressive effect on the expression of phytase-encoding genes.

Although the PSM applied for the initial screening for phytase-producing capabilities was likewise prepared using P8810, significant differences were nevertheless observed under the applied assay conditions. This may be attributed to local depletion of P_i in the proximate area surrounding the bacterial growth zones, thereby inducing the expression of phytase-encoding genes; an effect that would otherwise not occur in the liquid PSM.

6.5 Faba Bean Fermentations

Previous studies have demonstrated that fermentation mediated by *Bacillus* spp. can significantly decrease PA concentrations in legumes; an effect that has been attributed to the activity of endogenous phytases (Adebiyi et al., 2019; Adegbehingbe et al., 2014). Comparable findings were obtained in the present study, wherein both *B. subtilis* Natto and PRO55 exhibited a significant ability to reduce PA concentrations in FBM following fermentation. Although no significant reduction in PA was detected when comparing the 48-hour uninoculated control with the fermentations conducted with *B. subtilis* Natto and PRO55, the significant differences observed between these samples and the fermentation mediated by *B. subtilis* PRO120 suggest a possible contamination of the 48-hour uninoculated control. The results from this study indicate that fermentation mediated by strains of *B. subtilis* represents an effective strategy for reducing PA in legumes; however, strain-specific variation must be taken into account in this context.

To comprehensively assess the potential of *Bacillus*-mediated fermentation of plant-based proteinaceous foods to reduce PA content, it is essential to elucidate potential synergistic interactions through the investigation of co-culture fermentations involving multiple strains and/or species. Additionally, co-culture fermentations employing *Bacillus* and ascomycetous fungi or yeast have been reported highly efficient in other bioprocessing applications (T. Li et al., 2020; Rathod et al., 2025; S. Sharma et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022), yet their potential for PA hydrolysis has not been investigated hitherto, thereby constituting an additional avenue for research.

7 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that bacterial fermentation constitutes a viable and effective approach for improving the nutritional quality of plant-based foods through the degradation of PA. Genomic analyses successfully identified phytase-encoding genes across all investigated genera, including the first reported identification of the PTPHy-encoding gene, *phyLp*, in *Lactiplantibacillus*. Although strains belonging to *Limosilactobacillus* exhibited no detectable phytase activity, selected strains of *Bacillus* and *Lactiplantibacillus* demonstrated phytase-producing capacities in the initial screening assays.

In particular, *B. subtilis* Natto and PRO55 emerged as the most effective candi-

dates, achieving significant reductions in PA content within a faba bean-based food prototype. These findings indicate that, despite the widespread occurrence of phytase-encoding genes, strain-specific variation plays a decisive role in efficient hydrolysis of PA. Although challenges were encountered in the optimisation of phytase activity assays and in the identification of conserved PHO-box regulatory motifs, the study supports a foundational framework for the application of food-grade bacteria to enhance mineral and protein bioavailability in plant-based proteinaceous foods. Future research should therefore focus on species-specific validation of regulatory mechanisms as well as the investigation of synergistic co-culture fermentations to further optimise the reduction of PA in plant-based proteinaceous foods.

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9 Appendices

Appendix 1: *Bacillus* Consensus PHO-Box Sequences and Corresponding Motif

Species	Acc. No	Coordinates	Sequence
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	CP054415.1	2470105–2470067	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTGATTTATACGCATTTTACA
<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	CP150480.1	2596982–2596944	TTTACAAAACCTTTACATTTCGTTTAAAACGCCTTTTACA
<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i> BA59	CP024051.1	1893159–1893197	TTTACAAAACCTTTACATTTCGTTTAAAACGCCTTTTACA
<i>Bacillus cabrialesii</i>	CP096889.1	2498849–2498811	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTGATTTAAACCTTTTACA
<i>Bacillus halotolerans</i>	CP054584.1	2634078–2634040	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTCGATTTAAACCTATTTTACA
<i>Bacillus siamensis</i>	CP025001.1	1714294–1714332	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTCGATTTATACGCATTTTACA
<i>Bacillus spizizenii</i>	CP034943.1	2456191–2456153	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTCGATTTCAAACCCCTTTTACA
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	CP136402.1	2583118–2583080	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTCGGTTCAAACCCCTTTTACA
<i>Bacillus vallismortis</i>	CP033052.1	2551165–2551127	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTCAATACAAACCCCTTTTACA
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. BPAMC26568	CP060137.1	1380677–1380715	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTCGATTTAAACCATGTTTACA
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. BY1	CP030028.1	3483853–3483815	TTTACAAAACCTTTACAATCGATTTAAAACCCCTTAAACA
<i>Cytobacillus spongiae</i>	CP089997.1	2867068–2867032	TTTACAAAAGCTTTACATTTCGATTTAAACCAAGTTAATA
<i>Metabacillus dongyingensis</i>	CP082944.1	3567138–3567100	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTCGATTTAAAACCATGTTAACA
<i>Metabacillus</i> sp. McB07	CP069296.1	2807459–2807421	TTTACAAAACCTTAACATTTGATTTAAAACCATGTTAACA

Table S1: Sequences used to infer conserved motif for discovery of putative PHO-Boxes among strains in the bacterial collection.

Figure S1: Most highly conserved sequence motif identified using GLAM2 from the sequences listed in Table S1.

Appendix 2: Complete script for PHO-Box Discovery

```
for file in *.fasta
do
  ORGANISM_NAME=$(basename "$file" .fasta)

  # Gene prediction
  prodigal -i "$file" -o "${ORGANISM_NAME}.gff" -f gff -p single

  # Convert GFF to BED
  grep -v "#" "${ORGANISM_NAME}.gff" | awk '{OFS="\t"; print $1,$4-1,$5,$9
,0,$7}' > "${ORGANISM_NAME}.bed"

  # Genome index
  samtools faidx "$file"

  # Genome sizes
  cut -f1,2 "${file}.fai" > "${ORGANISM_NAME}.sizes"

  # Extract upstream regions
  bedtools flank -i "${ORGANISM_NAME}.bed" -g "${ORGANISM_NAME}.sizes" -l
300 -r 0 -s \
| awk '($3-$2) >= 16' > "${ORGANISM_NAME}_upstream300.bed"

  # Extract upstream sequences
  bedtools getfasta -fi "$file" -bed "${ORGANISM_NAME}_upstream300.bed" -s -
fo "${ORGANISM_NAME}_upstream300.fasta"

  # Motif scan
  glam2scan -2 -n 150 -o "G2S_${ORGANISM_NAME}_out" n \
"/Users/kristofferkrabbe/Desktop/Master thesis/Data/Sequencing data/
motif_PHO_box_Bacillus_glam.txt" \
"${ORGANISM_NAME}_upstream300.fasta"

done
```

Appendix 3: Quantified Phytase Activities

Table S2: Phytase activity determinations obtained during the diagnostic evaluation and optimisation of the K-PHYTASE phytase assay kit.

Sample ID	Phytase Activity (U/mL)
Unadjusted K-PHYTASE Assay	
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Intracellular	-0.009
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Extracellular	-0.005
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Intracellular	0.004
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular	0.007
Commercial Phytase (Positive Control)	15.210
Optimum β-Propeller Phytase Conditions	
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Intracellular	-0.002
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular	-0.002
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Intracellular (+CaCl ₂)	-0.007
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular (+CaCl ₂)	-0.004
Optimised Growth Conditions (V1)	
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular	0.001
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Extracellular	0.005
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO115, Extracellular	0.000
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO120, Extracellular	0.001
Commercial Phytase (Positive Control)	14.789
Optimised Growth Conditions (V2)	
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Intracellular	0.000
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular	-0.001
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Intracellular	0.002
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Extracellular	0.000
New Phytic Acid Source	
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular (1%)	-0.002
<i>B. subtilis</i> Natto, Extracellular (3%)	-0.010
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Extracellular (1%)	-0.010
<i>B. subtilis</i> PRO55, Extracellular (3%)	0.009
Commercial Phytase (Positive Control)	19.479

Appendix 4: Flow Diagram of Successive Modifications

Figure S2: Flow diagram outlining the successive modifications adopted during diagnostic evaluation and optimisation of the phytase activity assay.

10 AI Declaration

Declaration of using generative AI tools (for students)
<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> I/we have used generative AI as an aid/tool <i>(please tick)</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I/we have NOT used generative AI as an aid/tool <i>(please tick)</i></p> <p><i>If generative AI is permitted in the exam, but you haven't used it in your exam paper, you just need to tick the box stating that you have not used GAI. You don't have to fill in the rest.</i></p>
<p>List which GAI tools you have used and include the link to the platform (if possible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- ChatGPT 5.5: https://chatgpt.com/ (OpenAI)- NotebookLM: https://notebooklm.google/ (Google)- Research Assistant: https://soeg.kb.dk/discovery/ (Det Kgl. Bibliotek)
<p>Describe how generative AI has been used in the exam paper:</p> <p>ChatGPT 5.5 (OpenAI): <i>During the preparation of this MSc Thesis, 'ChatGPT 5.5' was used to provide detailed step-by-step recipes for preparation of reagents used in various experimental procedures. No generated content from this tool has been included in the final thesis manuscript.</i></p> <p>NotebookLM (Google): <i>During the preparation of this MSc Thesis, 'NotebookLM' was used as a tool to help understand complex scientific articles. In these cases, 'NotebookLM' provided explanatory summaries regarding results, methodologies, statements etc. that required further interpretation. No generated content from this tool has been included in the final thesis manuscript.</i></p> <p>Research Assistant (Det Kgl. Bibliotek): <i>During the preparation of this MSc Thesis, 'Research Assistant' was used as a tool to help search for relevant scientific literature, while providing brief summaries of key findings from the scientific articles in question. No generated content from this tool has been included in the final thesis manuscript.</i></p> <p><i>Please note: Content generated by GAI that is used as a source in the paper requires correct use of quotation marks and source referencing. Read the guidelines from Copenhagen University Library at KUnet.</i></p>